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for Fisheries Management - Final Report**

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The UN Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) reports that worldwide fisheries reached peak level of production in 1994. However, during the last decades a series of fish stocks have reached, or are close to, collapse in several parts of the world. The future viability of fisheries depends upon more complete understanding and monitoring of the interrelation and dependence of ecological and socio-economic factors related to the fisheries activities and exploitation of the marine food resources.

In 1997 the European Commission started an activity related to the development and distribution of the *Ecopath-with-Ecosim* food chain model – EwE - (Christensen & Pauly, 1993). This project included model development and validation through close interaction, use and validation by a worldwide group of experts from 20 nations. In the fisheries community, the EwE tools are used for studying and simulating marine trophic webs and mass balance, and for ecosystem management.

The European Commission funded Estimation of Primary Production for Fisheries Management (PROOF) project has produced estimates of European regional and ocean-basin scale marine phytoplankton primary production (PP) based on available ocean colour and temperature data from earth observation satellites for the period September 1997 to December 2002. A number of models were implemented and tested against archived and extensive project-specific *in situ* primary production estimates off the northwest of Spain, in the Celtic Sea, English Channel and in the Atlantic Ocean. The seasonal capabilities of the models were tested through a weekly sampling campaign in the western English Channel in 2001; the spatial characteristics used data obtained on a cruise between the UK and South Africa that covered a variety of trophic levels. The opportunity was taken to compare the PROOF model with a variety of models operated by leaders in the field within the NASA PPARR3 project. The sensitivity of the models has also been investigated. The spatial and temporal variability of the PP have been assessed and validated against state-of-the-art marine ecosystem models, based on the MICOM and HYCOM ocean circulation models.

Based on the requirements for the use of PROOF results in food-chain modelling such as EwE, the PROOF project selected and validated the algorithms to be used for production of results based on satellite Earth observation data and model output. The PP estimates and modelled parameters from the PROOF project have been prepared for use in the EwE marine food web model in order to assess the marine production at various levels in the food web. The data are also available via a web site with simple data extraction tools.

Finally, recommendations for model improvement and directions for future research are suggested.

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2 PROJECT SYNOPSIS

The PROOF (Estimation of Primary Production for Fisheries Management) project has produced estimates of the regional and ocean basin-scale marine primary production (PP) based on available ocean colour and temperature data from earth observation satellites. The spatial and temporal variability of the PP have been assessed and validated against state-of-the-art marine ecosystem models, based on the MICOM and HYCOM ocean circulation models. The PP estimates and modelled parameters from the PROOF project are prepared for use in the publicly available Ecopath-with-Ecosim (EwE) marine food web model (Christensen et al, 2000) in order to assess the marine production at various levels in the food web. Accordingly all major results of the PROOF project and their related data sets are published on the WWW (<http://www.nersc.no/PROOF>). The PROOF project has been successful in achieving its objectives. The higher-level production, such as fish production, is essential for proper management of fisheries, implementation of national and EC Common Fisheries Policy, as well as a basis for agreements on international quotas and fish catch regulations. The project intended to develop close relationships with the European fisheries management authorities at national, EC and international level in order to assure user guidance over the project results, however in this respect the PROOF project was less successful.

The **overall objectives** of the PROOF project were:

1. To provide estimates of marine primary production at regional (European waters) and ocean basin (North Atlantic ocean) scales from satellite ocean colour and temperature data. State-of-the-art algorithms will be implemented for the retrieval of chlorophyll-a concentration and primary production in open ocean (case I) and coastal (case II) waters, and validated and improved using both archived and new data obtained during the project. 3D-coupled physical biogeochemical models will be used to assess the spatial and temporal variability of the derived primary production.
2. To apply primary production to ecosystem modelling and guarantee an efficient dissemination and exploitation of the developed products. To disseminate into the

public domain, data sets on CD-ROM, including software for integration within common food chain and fish-stock prediction models.

3. To assess the impact of the above development in term of improved fisheries management in relation to the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), through model simulations. Direct interactions with the user community will gauge the usefulness and efficiency of the developed products.

In order to achieve these objectives the PROOF project were implemented in three phases summarised in Sections 2.1 to 2.3.

2.1 Proof-of-concept

In the Proof-of-Concept phase the PROOF project studied the Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) (Christensen et al., 2000) tool in order to identify the best approach to incorporate satellite and model derived information into the EwE. Mass balance budgets in the EwE are typically estimated for periods of one year. Accordingly the estimation of annual primary production and phytoplankton biomass should be provided as input to the EwE model system. However a sensitivity study concluded that seasonal variability may have a significant impact on the actual simulations of the EwE and predictions of the overall state of the ecosystem. Therefore the "Proof-of-Concept" concluded that relevant input information to the EwE based on satellite data and model simulations should include monthly, seasonal and annual values for the primary production and the phytoplankton biomass. Based on satellite data these parameters can be estimated for the surface layer of the oceans. Physical ocean parameters such as the mixed layer depth and vertical temperature profile as well as the vertical distribution of the phytoplankton biomass can be supported from model simulation output available within the PROOF consortium. Evaluation of the EwE in an open ocean and for the North Sea areas revealed a high sensitivity to the ecotrophic efficiency (EE), which is proportional to the production and varies significantly with the input biomass values used. Based on this study we conclude that an overall accuracy for the phytoplankton biomass of 30% and a primary production estimate of 50% is required for improved use of the EwE. These values are however significantly higher than the capabilities of current algorithms in use for retrieval of chlorophyll-a from satellite ocean colour data. A need to improve the

conversion from chlorophyll-a concentration to phytoplankton biomass was also identified.

Based on Proof-of-Concept the PROOF project decided to focus on improving the methods for primary production estimates from satellite data and providing phytoplankton profiles and physical ocean profiles such as temperature and mixed layer depth from model simulation output for use in the EwE.

2.2 Research development and implementation

The scientific work of PROOF are basically twofold; (i) improvements of the retrieval algorithms for estimation of chlorophyll-a, phytoplankton and primary production for satellite Earth observation data and (ii) Apply state-of-the-art marine ecosystem modelling for optimal retrieval of vertical profiles of the phytoplankton biomass, temperature profiles and mixed layer depth information. In the latter the MICOM and HYCOM ocean models were coupled to form a marine ecosystem model.

Originally ocean colour satellite data from SeaWiFS, Envisat MERIS and MODIS satellites were intended to be used in PROOF. Due to delays in launch and a lack of regular availability only SeaWiFS data were of practical use to the project. The validity of retrieval algorithms for chlorophyll-a from ocean colour data is significantly different in oceanic (Case 1) and turbid coastal (Case 2) waters. In order to meet the accuracy requirements the latest standard official version of the NASA SeaWiFS processing software (SeaDAS OC4v4) were used for oceanic waters. In Case 2 waters the optical signal is more complex and the standard NASA algorithms do not meet the required level of accuracy. Accordingly a more complex analytical approach based on Moore and Aiken (submitted) has been adopted for use in PROOF calculations in coastal waters. Four primary production models have been evaluated in the PROOF project: an empirical model, a depth integrated model and two wavelength-resolving models. Based on this the PROOF primary production models were set up using inputs of: 1) the *in situ* measured surface chlorophyll, with the assumption of a homogeneous vertical distribution, to mirror what can be measured from satellite; 2) the sea-surface temperature; 3) the surface irradiance obtained from the ECMWF cloud fields and 4) the local ambient pressure, humidity, ozone, precipitable water and wind speed extracted from SeaWiFS ancillary (NCEP) data. These PP models were comprehensively validated against *in situ* data for several regional and basin scale regions.

The primary production model based on the Morel (1991) model updated with the Morel *et al.*, (1996) modifications (“the LPCM model”) was selected for use within the PROOF project. The operational implementation of the LPCM model based on use of SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a, AVHRR-SST, irradiance and meteorological data resulted in the “*PROOF PP model*” used in the “production phase” of the PROOF project. Not planned in the PROOF project was the participation in the NASA supported Primary Production Algorithm Round Robin 3 wherein the PROOF PP model was compared with models operated by other laboratories. In both the Atlantic and Mediterranean the PROOF PP model estimates higher production than the mean of all the models: in the Atlantic the estimate is consistently ~10-20% and in the Mediterranean ~10% higher with the exception of the Summer months when production is up to 30% higher.

The ocean circulation and ecosystem modelling of PROOF was based on the state of the art coupled models at the Nansen Center. At the start of the PROOF project this was based on the MICOM isopycnic ocean model coupled with the biogeochemical module implemented and developed at the Nansen Center. This model configuration is denoted the DIADEM configuration developed and operated within the EC DIADEM project. For PROOF the DIADEM model output made the basis for an extensive validation effort of the ecosystem parameters (phytoplankton and primary production) versus *in situ* measurement provided by the OMEX-1 project. New geostatistical methods were implemented. A limitation of isopycnic models is the handling of the upper biological productive layers of the ocean as one bulk mixed layer. Therefore in order to better simulate phytoplankton and primary production in the water column an improved representation of the upper ocean layers is required. Accordingly an ocean model resolving the mixed layer was preferred for the PROOF simulations of the phytoplankton and temperature profiles of the upper part of the ocean. The Hybrid Coordinate Model (HYCOM) using z-layers in the physical mixed layer was implemented for the Atlantic Ocean and coupled with the same ecosystem model used in the DIADEM configuration. The PROOF ocean model simulations were performed for the North Atlantic Ocean basin providing 17 physical, biological and chemical ocean parameters in 22 vertical layers.

2.3 Production and demonstration

Based on the requirements for: (1) the use of the PROOF output in marine food-chain modelling in support of fisheries management and; (2) the project validation efforts of the selected algorithms, the production of PROOF data and model output were initiated.

Based on satellite information sources the PROOF project has produced primary production maps (in $\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) with 18 km spatial resolution for the following:

- monthly, seasonally and annually averaged maps covering the years from 1997 to 2002 for the entire globe, North Atlantic, Europe, Celtic Sea and English Channel.
- a climatology product corresponding to the average over the six years covered by the project.

Based on the HYCOM ocean model the following physical quantities are produced as weekly output and averaged to monthly, seasonal and annual values, for the North Atlantic Ocean:

- the vertical (depth) distribution of phytoplankton biomass,
- the vertical (depth) profile of water temperature,
- the mixed layer depth, which can be used to estimate the water layer where primary production is concentrated.

and the following biological quantities:

- the phytoplankton biomass (expressed as $\text{mmol N}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$),
- the 3-D spatial distribution of phytoplankton and zooplankton and detritus,

The PROOF database, available at <http://www.nersc.no/PROOF>, allows the extraction of the relevant physical and biological parameters for calculation of the annual marine primary production and its seasonal variability to be used as input into marine food chain modelling for use in fishery management.

3 STATEMENT OF COMPLIANCE

The PROOF project has, we believe, been a scientific success with the submission or publication of five manuscripts to peer reviewed scientific journals and one thesis defended for the “Doctor of Philosophy” at University of Southampton. Most parts of the scheduled scientific tasks of the PROOF project have been completed and ten out of 12 scheduled project deliverables have been completed and submitted to the EC; albeit with a short submission delay. At the time of the completion of the final report the project is seven months overdue. The major scientific results of the PROOF research activities are innovative and are applicable in accordance with the plan and expectations outlined in the Description of Work. In addition to the scheduled deliverables, the PROOF project has submitted other scientific results not initially envisaged.

A deficiency of the PROOF project realization was the inability to establish direct cooperation with its identified user communities – fisheries management and research, i.e. the “Ecopath user community”. This task was primarily the responsibility of Terra Orbit AS. It was planned to be achieved through two workshops (WP2), scheduled in the early and late phases of the project, to present respectively the plans and results of the PROOF project to its potential users. Neither of the two workshops have been held - the first because of lack of positive responses to participate in a planning workshop and the second due to the delays in the scientific deliverables from PROOF. The PROOF project was, however presented at the EuroOCEAN 2000 conference in Hamburg, reaching potential users in the science community and the European Commission. Accordingly, two scheduled user workshop reports (D.2 and D.9) have not been delivered to the Commission.

The time delay in the completion of the project tasks is due to several reasons: difficulty in the recruitment of dedicated project staff at PML; change in the ocean model tools from MICOM to HYCOM at NERSC; and sick staff during the overdue phase and final reporting of the project. These issues have further caused delay in the final completion of the PROOF project deliverables, which accordingly have had implications for the initiation of the user promotion activities scheduled towards the end of the project.

3.1 Project Deliverables

According to the Description of Work the following project deliverables were scheduled for the PROOF project and their actual time of delivery or not is indicated in the below table:

Deliverable No	Deliverable title	Scheduled Delivery (month)	Actual Delivery (month)	Nature
D1	Proof-of-concept – report, including a detailed specification of selected methodologies to be implemented in the realisation phase	10	1 st Ann.rep (18) D1 (36) *	Report / Method
D2	First user workshop report	10	NOT**	(Report)
D3	Chlorophyll algorithms for the selected European regions Primary production algorithm for the selected European regions	18	24	Report / Method
D4	Production line estimating primary production in Atlantic ocean basin Production line estimating primary production European waters	24	41***	Report
D5	Validated production line	27	41***	Prototype
D6	Chlorophyll depth-profile for PP models	27	42***	Simulation output
D7	Mixed layer depth and temperature for PP models	27	42***	Simulation output
D8	Model validation and error estimates Interpolation/extrapolation method	27	44***	Report / Method
D9	Second user workshop report	27	NOT**	(Report)
D10	Maps of ocean basin-scale, seasonal and annual primary production Maps of regional, seasonal and annual primary production CD-ROM with maps <i>in situ</i> data & conversion software	36	44***	Graphics / Data extraction tool
D11	User Guide for integration into Ecopath	36	44 ***	Report
D12	Publications and final report	36	44	Report / Publications

* Internally working document available since month 12, used as input to design WP3.

** Not delivered as scheduled to the Commission.

*** Available internally during period May to September 2003, Submitted to EC with the final report in October 2003.

3.2 Status of Work packages

The following objectives and specified description of work were identified for the scientific WP's in the PROOF DoW and a summary of the reported achievements follows:

WP0: Management (NERSC)
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assure completion of the project according to the expectations of EC. • Assure proper communication and co-ordination between the partners and the referee group. • Assure high-level quality control procedures for the project execution and deliverables.
<p>Description of work</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maintain communication with EC project management. 2. Delegate and assure that the various tasks to be completed are sufficiently understood and agreed with the subcontractor. 3. Maintain control of the progress and communication between the project participants and the referee group. 4. Make minutes from the project meetings. 5. Provide duplication of all reports and deliverables from the project. 6. Maintain back up of all project deliverables during and after the completion of the project. 7. Implement and maintain procedures for project quality control.

*Status WP0: **Mainly done.** Annual management reports, MoM prepared and submitted with some delays according to schedule. Project deliverables edited, duplicated and submitted to EC when available from responsible partner(s). No PROOF Referee Group established and accordingly not coordinated the activities of this group (item 2).*

WP1: Proof-of-concept (Lead NERSC)
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To assess the constraints and define an optimal level of accuracy as required for estimation of the satellite derived primary production in order to match the performance characteristics of the ecosystem (food-chain) model • Assess how uncertainties in the primary production affect computations in the ecosystem (food-chain) model. • Assess how satellite-derived primary production can be implemented and used in the context of Ecopath and assessment of accuracy for use Ecosim food chain and mass balance simulation model.
<p>Description of work</p> <p>WP 1.1: Sensitivity test of the ecosystem (food-chain) model (Ecopath) (NERSC)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of specific cases for simulation to evaluate the model performance under various conditions. • Perform and evaluate model simulations under the various defined test cases of variations <p>WP 1.2: Feasibility study of the EO data derived primary production. (NERSC / PML)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of CHL retrieval algorithms for case I and case II waters: where is it possible to derive acceptable accuracy on estimate of PP from ocean colour data. • Simple test of use of PP estimated from SeaWiFS data (provided by PML and processed with existing non-optimised standard algorithm) in Ecopath (NERSC).

*Status WP1: **Done** – Joint work between NERSC and PML, see D1 and herein. WP1 activities have contributed to the development of WP3 and D1 results has been used internally during the project implementation (see 1st Annual report), but officially submitted as a formal deliverable very late to EC (month 36).*

WP2: User Workshops (Lead Terra Orbit)

<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop with ecosystem (food-chain) model users, including fisheries representatives. • Obtain information on the ecosystem (food-chain) model users expectations for inclusion of satellite derived primary production estimates in their model use.
<p>Description of work</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invite approx. 8 - 10 selected (most relevant) users/experts to the workshops. The participation to the second workshop will be opened to a larger community (TO) • Establish a voluntarily project reference group (mainly from the expert institutions) to perform a later project referee evaluation of the project (TO). • Prepare and host workshop, including project presentation and expected out come and generation of discussion for input to the project (All).

*Status WP2: **Not completed as scheduled** – no D2 deliverable submitted. Several registered users of the Ecopath software, included its developers, were contacted in order to participate in the first PROOF users workshop, however no or negative replies were received from most invited scientists. Accordingly, the basis for participation was absent and the 1st Users workshop was cancelled. This had implications for the further interaction with this as a reference group for the project, but not on the progress and work achieved in PROOF. Only parts of the allocated personnel resources (preparatory activities for the 1st Workshop) and none of the direct expenses have been used within the project.*

WP3: Remote sensing algorithms (Lead PML)

<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop, implement and validate a production line for integrated use of satellite-derived primary production information in the ecosystem (food-chain) model. • Develop and validate the best-suited retrieval algorithms to derive chlorophyll-a from SeaWiFS (and MODIS & MERIS) ocean colour data for specified regions. • Identify an operational algorithm to derive PP from ocean colour data that is suitable for use in ecosystem (food-chain) model • Test and validate the integrated algorithm (CHL + PP algorithms) for the retrieval of primary production
<p>Description of work</p> <p>WP 3.1 Review, evaluation and development of CHL algorithms (PML)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For case I waters, review and select CHL algorithms (PML). <p><i>Done – see D3 and herein.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For case II waters, develop optical model-based approaches to retrieval of water leaving radiance and inherent optical properties for calculation of CHL (PML). <p><i>Completed - Case II optical model implemented and paper submitted for publication (Moore & Aiken, 2003).</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquire recent level 2 and 3 products from NASA for which PML and NERSC are both authorised research users of SeaWiFS data (PML / NERSC) <p><i>Completed – SeaWiFS data for entire mission are available at PML and used in D10.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select and provide historical test data sets of satellite-derived CHL from CZCS climatological data. <p><i>Completed – all CZCS data from mission area available at PML.</i></p>

<p>WP 3.2 Review and evaluation of PP algorithms (PML)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of LPCM and VGPM models (PML) <p><i>Done – see results in D4 and herein; code delivered in D5.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent and comparative evaluations of both models (PML / NERSC) <p><i>Deliverables exceeded – see D4 and herein; LPCM and VGPM compared to in situ data sets and each for regional and basin scale cases as planned; additional deliverable: PROOF PP model intercompared with 35 other models as part of PPARR3.</i></p> <p>WP 3.3 Algorithm for ocean basin-scale PP (PML).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consolidate WP 3.2 results into a production line. <p><i>Done – see D10 and results herein.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check depth integrated models (VGPM), which may be more appropriate in particular cases. <p><i>Done – see comparisons in D4 and herein.</i></p>

*Status WP3: **Done** – see D3 and D4 and herein. Results have been published or submitted for an external scientific review. Delays in completion of deliverables.*

<p>WP4: Numerical modelling (Lead NERSC)</p> <p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Derive improved estimates of PP in selected regions based on simulation with the biogeochemical model • To perform an assessment of the error sources, their magnitude and sensitivity in the derived data products for various regions and conditions • To perform an assessment of the impact of these errors in the ecosystem (food-chain) model. <p>Description of work</p> <p>WP 4.1: Estimation of parameters, numerical simulations (NERSC)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulation of typical depth-profile of chlorophyll concentration for use in LPCM model (NERSC). <p><i>Done – see joint D6 and D7 data base and results herein.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulation of the mixed layer depth for use in VGPM model, in conjunction with SST (NERSC). <p><i>Done – see joint D6 and D7 data base and results herein.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulation of carbon cycle and primary production in the selected regions (NERSC). <p><i>Not done, due to D1 recommendation of use of primary production from satellite data and phytoplankton biomass from models.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulation of temporal and spatial variability of primary production in selected regions (NERSC). <p><i>Not done, due to D1 conclusion (see above).</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accounting for the ocean dynamics for better extrapolation of PP values in regions with a lack of <i>in situ</i> measurements (NERSC). <p><i>Done – see D8 and results herein. Data available in joint D6 and D7 data base.</i></p> <p>WP 4.2: Validation and error estimates (PML)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select and provide <i>in situ</i> observations (PML / NERSC)

<p><i>Done - OMEX I data and DIADEM model output used in D8.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of SeaWiFS-derived ocean basin-scale PP using <i>in situ</i> observations (PML / NERSC) <p><i>Done – see results herein and Tilstone et al submitted (D4-Appendix).</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional validation of SeaWiFS derived PP using PML data sources (PML) <p><i>Done – regional comparison with data from NW Spanish coast; also see WP5 below.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimates of absolute and relative range and accuracy of PP (PML / NERSC) <p><i>Done – D8 and results herein.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitivity analysis of the algorithms implemented (PML / NERSC). <p><i>Done – see results herein and Tilstone et al submitted (D4-Appendix).</i></p>
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*Status WP4: **Mainly done** – see joint D6 and D7 database and D8 model validation report as well as results herein. The model simulations excluded the primary production, due to D1 “Proof-of-Concept” recommendation to use primary production from satellite data and phytoplankton biomass from model output. Results used in two papers – Joint et al, (2002) and Tilstone et al (submitted).*

WP5: Regional remote sensing algorithms and in situ validation (Lead NERSC)
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testing, validation and refinement of the integrated algorithm (CHL + PP algorithms) for the retrieval of primary production for selected regions.
<p>Description of work</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of two regional test areas from European LME, which are representative of continental shelf and an upwelling area cases (PML). • Undertake <i>in situ</i> observation of primary production (using radiocarbon techniques) and associated variables in Atlantic Ocean (SeaWiFS cal/val cruises, including Atlantic Meridional Transect - AMT) and European waters (Celtic Sea and western English Channel). Full use will be made of archived PP data obtained in the Celtic Sea and west of Spain through EU funding (OMEX I and II) (PML). <p><i>Done – three regional test areas selected: NW Spanish upwelling area; western English Channel and Celtic Sea. Use made of archived in situ data obtained during SeaWiFS mission. Extensive, weekly observation of primary production in western English Channel in 2001. Ten day cruise in Celtic Sea undertaken in 2000. Analysis of data obtained in Atlantic Ocean SeaWiFS cal/val cruises. Two submitted peer review papers Woods et al (2003) and Tilstone et al . (2003)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use WP 4 outputs in order to derive characteristic vertical profiles in areas of no other information, and hydrodynamics information (NERSC). <p><i>Done – available in joint D6 and D7 data base.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coupling and testing of the algorithms (PML). <p><i>Done – quality check of D5.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of the produced results in conjunction with WP 2 (Second User Workshop) and WP 4.2 (NERSC / PML).

Not completed, see WP2.

*Status WP5: **Mainly done** – see D4 and its Appendix two submitted publications Woods et al (2003) and Tilstone et al (2003). D5 the validate software for the production.*

WP6: Production (Lead PML)

- Objectives**
- Production of a set of maps of ocean basin-scale, monthly, seasonal and annual primary production (1° x 1° grid)
 - Production of a set of maps of regional, monthly, seasonal and annual primary production for the selected regions (North Atlantic and European waters)
 - Develop user-friendly software for integration of satellite-derived primary production in the Ecopath ecosystem (food-chain) model.

- Description of work**
- Production of CHL and PP maps (**PML**)
 - Implementation of software for integration of PP maps into the Ecopath (food-chain) model (**NERSC**)

*Status WP6: **Done** – see D10, PROOF results website and results presented herein. Satellite data: standalone programme written at PML to extract primary production value for given latitude, longitude and time from PP maps; also implemented on PML website. Modelled data: standalone programme written at NERSC to extract vertical profiles of phytoplankton concentration and temperature as well as mixed layer depth for given latitude, longitude and time from model simulations implemented with as web-interface.*

WP7: Dissemination and exploitation (Lead TO)

- Objectives**
- To disseminate the results and activities of the project to the outside (FAO, national ministries of agriculture and fisheries, EC directorate - DG VIII, XI, XII, XIV, Fisheries research community),
 - To assess the sustainability of a commercial service.

- Description of work**
- Project web-site design and implementation (**TO**)
Done – <http://www.nersc.no/PROOF>
 - Documentation of software (**NERSC / PML**)
Done – see D5 and D11
 - Embedding in a visual basic Windows interface (**TO**)
Done – web based interfaces have been implemented.
 - Preparation of demonstration (**TO**)
Partly done – Project conclusions summarized in this Final report. PROOF results and data base made available at project web site <http://www.nersc.no/PROOF>.
 - Production of 200 copies of CD-ROMs including the produced maps, available *in situ* measurements for selected regions, software (NASA must provide an authorisation for eventual redistribution of SeaWiFS data) (**TO**)
Done/Open - Maps and data made available through the project web-site. To be agreed by EC to replace

CD-ROM version with a web dissemination interface (technology change since proposal submission).

- Publication of scientific and non-scientific articles (**All**)

Done: a total of 5 peer-reviewed papers acknowledge EU support of PROOF and were completed within the project, in addition there was one PhD (Woods, 2003) and 8 non peer reviewed papers.

- Generation of articles and publications informing on the project activities and conclusions (**All**).

Done – publication or submission of 5 peer-reviewed papers; one PhD thesis; 3 posters; 5 presentations: see Section 3.3.

*Status WP7: **Partly completed** – see this D12 final report, D5 and D11, web-site disseminated results (<http://www.nersc.no/PROOF>), Five published and submitted peer review manuscripts and one PhD thesis. A deficiency is the lack presentation of the final results to the users due to very late completion of the project final results and deliverables, which will be done through post project presentations of PROOF at scientific conferences (e.g. ICES 2004).*

3.3 PROOF Publication Status

In addition to the scheduled PROOF report and data deliverables the project have also produced the following scientific communication deliverables in terms of peer review articles and other non-review literature and communications.

3.3.1 Peer Reviewed Articles

Authors	Title	Journal	Reference
Joint, I., Groom, S., Wollast, R., Lei Chou, Tilstone, G., Figueiras, F., Loijens, M. and Smyth, T.	The response of phytoplankton production to periodic upwelling and relaxation events at the Iberian shelf break: estimates by the ¹⁴ C method and by satellite remote sensing.	Journal of Marine Systems	2002, Vol. 32, pp: 219-238
Podznyakov, D.V., K.Ya. Kondratyev, L.H. Pettersson	Remote sensing assessment of phytoplankton primary productivity: Methodological Aspects	Earth Obs. and Remote Sensing, Harwood Academic Publisher	Vol. 16, No. 4, pp. 527-540, 2001
Moore G. and J. Aiken	A bio-optical model for the determination of inherent optical properties from reflectance data: applications to remotely sensed data from case I and case II waters.	Applied Optics	In press
G. H. Tilstone, T. J. Smyth, F. G. Figueiras, R. G. Barlow, S. B. Groom	A comparison of measured and remotely sensed estimates of primary production in the eastern Atlantic Ocean.	Marine Ecology Progress Series	Submitted 2003

Woods, Katharine, Andrew P Rees, Peter I Miller and Ian Joint	The influence of water mass characteristics on phytoplankton production in the Celtic Sea	Continental Shelf Research	Submitted 2003
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3.3.2 Non refereed literature/communication/reports:

Authors / Editors	Title	Event	Reference	Type ¹
Woods K.	Development and assessment of novel techniques to measure primary production in the Celtic Sea and English Channel	Dissertation, February 2003	University of Southampton	Ph.D. Thesis
Johannessen, O.M., L.H. Pettersson, D. Durand, S. Groom, G. Moore and G. Jevne	PROOF - Estimation of Primary Production for Fisheries Management	EU EuroOCEAN 2000 conference	Eur 19359 ISBN 92-828-9713-3	Poster / proceedings
Woods, K., Johannessen, O.M., L.H. Pettersson, D. Durand, S. Groom, I. Joint and G. Jevne	PROOF - Estimation of Primary Production for Fisheries Management	UK Parliament, London, 2000		Poster
Pettersson, L. and Durand, D., O. M. Johannessen, I. Joint, S. Groom, K. Woods, T. Smyth, G. Moore and G. Jevne	Satellite-Derived Primary Production as a Driven Parameter in Simulation of Fisheries Dynamics	29 th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of the Environment, Buenos Aires, Argentina, 8-12 April 2002	CD-ROM publication ISRSE	Oral & poster presentation
Pettersson, L. and Durand, D., O. M. Johannessen, I. Joint, S. Groom, K. Woods, T. Smyth, G. Moore and G. Jevne	Satellite-Derived Primary Production as a Driven Parameter in Simulation of Fisheries Dynamics	ECMWF conference, Cambridge, May 2002		Oral presentation
Woods, K., I. Joint, S. Groom and P. Holligan	A seasonal study of primary production in the Western English Channel and comparison with remote sensing estimates	Challenger Centenary Conference: Marine Science 2002, Plymouth, September 2002		Oral presentation accepted
Woods, K., I. Joint, S. Groom and P. Holligan	A time-series of photosynthesis and productivity in the Western English Channel as measured by three different techniques	Int. conference on "Phytoplankton productivity: An Appreciation of 50 Years of the Study of Production in Oceans and Lakes", Bangor, March 2002		Oral presentation
Inizan, M.	Geostatistical validation of a marine ecosystem model using <i>in situ</i> data	Thesis Ecole de Mine de Paris	NERSC, Special report	Report

¹ Type: Abstract, Newsletter, Oral Presentation, Paper, Poster, Proceedings, Report, Thesis.

4 FISH-STOCK ASSESSMENT: TOOLS, BOTTLENECKS AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

The UN Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) reports that worldwide fisheries reached peak level of production in 1994. However, during the last decades a series of fish stocks have reached, or are close to, collapse in several parts of the world. The future viability of fisheries depends upon more complete understanding and monitoring of the interrelation and dependence of ecological and socio-economic factors related to the fisheries activities and exploitation of the marine food resources. The legal basis of the EC formulation of a Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) is based on the Articles 38 to 43 in the European Treaty. The planning and regulations of the EC fisheries are performed under DG XIV – Fisheries, although also major concern to the fisheries policy is a focus of DG VIII – Development, and in particular the relation to the resources in the Developing countries. The fisheries resources are of global nature and concern, hence around 40% of the total CFP spending is related to activities in non-EC waters.

In 1993, the EC DG VIII started a series of actions to contribute to a global sustainable management of fisheries and aquaculture. One of these actions is the ACP-EC Fisheries Research Initiative that aims to promote interdisciplinary research on fisheries and aquaculture in support to researchers and managers in African, Caribbean and Pacific (ACP) countries, with the sustainable management of living aquatic resources and conservation of aquatic bio-diversity as main goals. As an accompanying action, in 1997 the EC started an activity related to the development and distribution of the Ecopath-with-Ecosim food chain model – EwE - (Christensen & Pauly, 1993) (INCO-DC funded concerted action “Placing fisheries resources in their ecosystem context: Co-operation, comparisons, and human impact”), as well as the implementation of the FishBase database. This project included model development and validation through close interaction, use and validation by a worldwide group of experts from 20 nations. The Ecopath model and its simulation part Ecosim are currently widely used in the fisheries community as a tool for studying and simulating marine trophic webs and mass balance, and for ecosystem management, both within Europe and world-wide. It is routinely used for exploring consequences of alternative fishery management strategies, including optimal stocking,

refuges, and changes in exploitation. The model simulates ecosystem management in response to fishing and/or environmental change, and provides a hypothesis-testing framework.

Whilst significant progress has been made in modelling the biomass and abundance at high trophic level (fish), less attention has been given to the lower trophic levels, and in particular to the marine primary production, for which currently the best estimates of global primary production vary by a factor 2, and no reliable estimates exist in coastal regions. Until recently, it was commonly believed that primary production was not a limiting factor for fish stock sustainability since only 2.2 % of the world's aquatic primary production was required to sustain the fisheries (Pauly & Christensen, 1995). Therefore, human exploitation of marine resource seems insufficient by itself to alter on a large scale any but the target populations. However, Pauly & Christensen (1995) has shown that a more realistic value of the global aquatic primary production required (PPR) to sustain fisheries was 8.0 %, with values up to 35 % in upwelling and shelf systems. The nearshore systems, readily accessible to humans, have thus very high primary production requirement, nearing that estimated for terrestrial systems. The lack of good estimates of primary production is currently a limitation to optimal fish stock assessment, in particular in the coastal regions where the PPR is very high (comm. DG VIII).

Therefore, an improved knowledge of ocean basin-scale and regional primary production and its temporal and spatial variability will, in the longer term, lead to a significant improvement of the management tools (in this project defined as the Ecopath model). Such knowledge should lead to better estimates of input parameters for food-chain and fish stock modelling. A direct consequence should be the production of more reliable predictive information to fisheries, with possible impact on national and international decision-making and fisheries policy.

On the one hand, the ocean colour sensors provide a unique spatial and temporal mapping of the variability of the upper ocean phytoplankton pigments under cloud free conditions, which has been demonstrated through several applications since the CZCS period. The uncertainty in chlorophyll pigment estimates is, however, an issue of great concern and has limited a wider use of the data beyond EO expert groups.

On the other hand, 3-D numerical model of marine ecosystems has shown a high potential for global simulations of the biological activity in the ocean. The two approaches

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are complementary. Therefore a combined approach seems to be the most promising to obtain a significant improvement in estimating primary production at global, regional and local scales.

5 OCEAN COLOUR AND PRIMARY PRODUCTION ALGORITHMS

At the start of PROOF there was only one ocean colour sensor, SeaWiFS, in orbit capable of providing the input data for regional and global scale investigation of primary production, and, hence, effort was focussed on this instrument. During the project MODIS data started to become available but, arguably, SeaWiFS was not superseded by MODIS until after the completion of PROOF. MERIS data from the ESA Envisat spacecraft were also unavailable during the project.

5.1 *Chlorophyll algorithm*

5.1.1 Case 1 Waters

Case 1 waters have optical properties dominated by phytoplankton and associated detrital material with little influence of terrestrial coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) or suspended particulate matter (SPM), either re-suspended bottom material or advected into the region. Hence, oceanic and shelf stratified waters are usually case 1. Algorithms to retrieve chlorophyll concentration in case 1 waters are well characterised (O'Reilly, *et al.*, 1998). The standard NASA SeaWiFS algorithm called OC4v4 has been chosen for this study since, first, the algorithm has been developed and improved by scientists around the world (including PML) during the SeaWiFS mission. Second, regional algorithms were considered (e.g. Smyth *et al.*, 2002) for specific LME's, but these are limited by paucity of data (compared to the data sets used to construct OC4v4) and may be affected by statistical fluctuations. Finally, by using OC4v4, PROOF-processed SeaWiFS images will have identical chlorophyll values to images processed by NASA and other users of the SeaWiFS processing software (SeaDAS). Note that, initially, the OC4 algorithm was chosen for PROOF; however, with the release of the improved OC4v4, all regional SeaWiFS images were reprocessed with the new algorithm.

The OC4v4 algorithm is a band-switching algorithm that uses the maximum of three remote sensing reflectance (R_{rs}) ratios:

$$R = \log_{10}(\max(R_{rs\ 443}/R_{rs\ 555}, R_{rs\ 490}/R_{rs\ 555}, R_{rs\ 510}/R_{rs\ 555}))$$

$$Chl = 10^{(a_0 + a_1 * R + a_2 * R^2 + a_3 * R^3) + a_4}$$

The accuracy of SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a retrieval is approximately 35% in Case I water in match-ups with strict comparison criteria (< 1hour difference between satellite and in situ measurement; only full resolution SeaWiFS data considered). An example image calculated with the OC4 algorithm is shown in Figure 8.2.

5.1.2 Case 2 Waters

In case II waters the optical signal is more complex and affected by phytoplankton, CDOM and SPM in varying fractions, and the standard NASA algorithms do not work. Hence, for these waters a more complex analytical approach will be used based on Moore and Aiken (submitted).

The algorithm uses a theoretical-based, bio-optical model, which operates universally in case I waters (biogenic constituents only) or case II waters (with SPM and CDOM of terrestrial origin) by deriving the $a(\lambda)$ and $b_b(\lambda)$. The analytical solutions are achieved by unique parameterisations of the spectral slopes of the bio-optical variables. Since these spectral slopes are explicit inputs to the model, the model can be regionally tuned where there are known anomalous bio-optical conditions such as the Baltic Sea.

The algorithm uses the bi-directional reflectance, ρ_w expressed in terms of the physical properties of the water column rather than biogeochemical proxies (e.g. Chl-*a*). These are the IOPs, back-scattering, $b_{bt}(\lambda)$, from water and detritus (including suspended particles) and absorption, $a_t(\lambda)$, due to phytoplankton pigments, detritus (including suspended particles) dissolved compounds and water. The water reflectance ρ_w at any wavelength (λ) and for all geometry (sun angle, θ_s , view (scan) angle θ_v , and azimuth difference $\Delta\phi$) is related to the IOPs, $b_{bt}(\lambda)$ and $a_t(\lambda)$ by a quasi-linear relationship (Morel and Gentili, 1991, 1993 and 1996):

$$\rho_w = \pi \mathfrak{R}(f/Q)(\theta_s, \theta_v, \Delta\phi)(b_{bt}/a_t)$$

There are second order non-linear processes e.g. fluorescence and Raman scattering, that can be modelled (Mobley, 1994), but they are omitted from version 1 of the model, and will be implemented for version 2. Resorting to IOPs simplifies some of the complexities such

as phytoplankton pigment packaging, which results in variability of the pigment specific absorption coefficient, and allows the use of published data and field observations to determine phytoplankton pigment concentrations, rather than empirical relationships.

At the crux of the model is the observation that the values of total absorption, $a_t(\lambda)$, and by implication the apparent optical property, K_d , are highly auto-correlated spectrally, for visible wavelengths. This robust correlation has been observed for ac-9 measurements (Barnard *et al.* 1998, 1999) and for K_d (Austin and Petzold 1984, 1986) for a wide range of oceanographic provinces, and has been exploited to determine IOPs from reflectance data using triple ratios (Barnard *et al.*, 1999). Likewise the scattering and by implication back-scattering are highly auto-correlated spectrally, since they either obey a power law (case I waters) or are spectrally flat (case II waters). The auto-correlation of both b_{bt} and a_t , reduces the degrees of freedom in spectral reflectance. It is this constraint that enables the determination of the dominant absorbing compounds (e.g. pigments) from reflectance band-ratio algorithms. A basic principle of the IOP model is that, given knowledge of the spectral slope of absorption in any two wave bands, the absolute values of backscatter and absorption can be solved analytically from the values of reflectance. As opposed to simple ratio algorithms, this analytical solution is dependant on the viewing geometry and the terms f/Q above. In order to solve these equations it is necessary to determine iteratively the value of f/Q from the values of absorption and backscatter derived. These values of f/Q and \mathfrak{R} are determined from the Hydrolight radiative transfer code (Mobley 1995) and stored in look up tables (LUTS). The LUTs are calculated for sensor view angles (θ_v), solar zenith angles (θ_s) and azimuth difference angles ($\Delta\phi$), and for a range of $a(\lambda)$ and for $b(\lambda)$. These tables are used to determine the f/Q from absorption and hence the remotely sensed reflectance for any view or sun angle. Tables are also derived for subsurface ρ_w and irradiance reflectance, so that the model can be validated using *in-situ* observations from instruments.

Since phytoplankton absorption is independent of b_b , the derivation of chlorophyll and pigment concentrations presents a simple linear inversion of $a(\lambda)$. The absorption at each wavelength can be expressed as linear combinations of the constituents e.g.:

$$a(443) = a_p + a_{dy} \quad ; \quad a_p = (a_{chl}^*[\text{Chl-}a] + a_{psc}^*[\text{PSC}] + a_{ppc}^*[\text{PPC}])$$

These equations can be solved for the concentrations of the pigments if the *in vivo* specific absorptions of the pigment classes are known. At present these are not known with sufficient accuracy. Coefficients, derived empirically from multiple linear regressions using reflectance and HPLC data from the AMT cruises, are used for the determination of PPC and PSC. The combined detrital and CDOM (a_{dy}) can be solved using their spectral slopes:

$$\text{CDOM} = D1.a(412) - D2.a(443) \text{ (absorption units; m}^{-1}\text{)}$$

where D1 and D2 are derived analytically using the spectral slopes of phytoplankton, and combined detritus / CDOM.

Similarly in coastal waters CDOM absorption can be derived from $a(443)$ and $a(490)$, since $\rho_w(412)$ is often below detection limits, since CDOM abundance is high:

The Chl-*a* concentration is derived from $a(443)$, corrected for CDOM absorption determined as:

$$\text{Chl-}a = A1.a_p(443)^B \text{ (mg.m}^{-3}\text{)}$$

where A1 is the Chl-*a* concentration, corresponding to an $a_p(443)$ of 1.0, and B is an exponent of approximately 1.5, that can be determined from climatological data or from Bricaud *et al* (1995, 1998). In case II sediment dominated waters there will be no erroneous effects from the SPM as the algorithm is independent of the particle backscatter b_b , the same is true for coccolithophore patches where b_b is also high, and ratio algorithms erroneous estimates of Chl-*a* (Ackleson *et al*, 1994).

Optical and phytoplankton pigment data from the spatially-extensive, multi-ecosystem, AMT cruises (Aiken *et al*, 2000) and from coastal campaigns in the Western English Channel off Plymouth (E.U, COLORS) have been used to provide validation of the model.

5.2 Primary productions algorithms

5.2.1 Introduction

Behrenfeld and Falkowski (1997a) defined four classes of primary production algorithms and models based on their levels of integration, viz:

1. Depth Integrated
2. Time integrated
3. Wavelength integrated
4. and Wavelength resolving

In PROOF two of the most commonly used algorithms were investigated comprising of a depth integrated model proposed by Behrenfeld and Falkowski (1997a) and a wavelength resolving model first described by Morel (1991). These are described below along with a simple empirical model that was initially used at PML prior to PROOF.

5.2.2 Empirical Models

The simplest approach to the estimation of primary production from satellite-derived chlorophyll concentration relies on a strong correlation between surface chlorophyll concentration and depth-integrated primary production. Eppley *et al.*, (1985) simply regressed ^{14}C uptake rates against chlorophyll concentration and prior to the PROOF project this approach was taken by Joint and Groom (2000) and Joint *et al.*, (2001) in studies of primary production of the western English Channel (WEC) and central Celtic Sea $\sim 50^\circ\text{N}$ (two of the areas chosen for the PROOF regional studies). In the western English Channel estimates were restricted to the spring and summer months since the presence of suspended particulate matter has an effect on chlorophyll retrievals between October and March in these waters and low sun-angle causes problems with the atmospheric correction in this period. A good agreement was found between estimates of primary production derived by traditional ship-based measurements and from satellite-derived chlorophyll concentration (Joint and Groom, 2000). However, construction of empirical algorithms requires *in situ* data spread throughout the year and may not be applicable to other areas. Notably, this approach was also used in the OMEX II-II project (see OMEX final report, 2000) and a good correlation was found between $\log_{10}\text{C}$ and $\log_{10}\text{PP}$ but the regression coefficients were different from those found in the WEC, possibly due to the different light regime between the two regions. Therefore, the empirical approach may be of use where there are

extensive existing data sets, but for inputting data to Ecopath (i.e. the goal of PROOF) it must be assumed that there may not be extensive data available for a given region. Hence, this approach was abandoned in favour of models that better include irradiance and temperature. Note that since these more complex models were implemented in PROOF after the completion of the OMEX II-II project, but before the publication of results from the project in the scientific literature, we were able to completely update the paper using the PROOF PP model at the revision stage (see Joint et al, 2002)

5.2.3 The VGPM Model

The Vertically Generalised Production Model (VGPM) of Behrenfeld and Falkowski (1997a,b) was initially proposed as a candidate algorithm for PROOF. The VGPM calculates net primary production as:

$$\sum NPP = P_{opt}^B \times C_{sat} \times DL \times Z_{eu} \times F$$

where Z_{eu} is the euphotic depth, C_{sat} is the satellite surface chlorophyll concentration, D_{irr} is the daily photo-period, F is the light factor, and P_{opt}^B is the optimal rate of daily carbon fixation within the water column. P_{opt}^B is modelled according to a 7th order polynomial temperature-dependent relationship, thus, reference to temperature is implicitly included in P_{opt}^B . The model assumes that surface observations of temperature and chlorophyll are uniform throughout the mixed layer and that the maximum potential primary productivity is a function of temperature only. With these assumptions P_{opt}^B may conveniently be estimated from remote sensing measurements of sea surface temperature (SST).

After implementation and testing the VGPM was found to give primary production estimates consistently above *in situ* values and so was rejected in favour of the LPCM model. However, for completeness the LPCM model results are also compared herein with the VGPM.

5.2.4 The LPCM Model

The LPCM model was first proposed by Morel (1991):

$$PP = 12 a_{\max}^* \varphi_{\mu, \max} \int_0^{D z_{eu}} \int_0^{700} C(z) PUR(z, t, \lambda) f(I_0(z, t)) d\lambda dz dt$$

where PP is primary production, integrated to the base of the euphotic zone, $C(z)$ is the vertical chlorophyll profile, PUR is the photosynthetically usable radiation (spectral PAR weighted by the spectral phytoplankton absorption), f is a function that relates carbon production to usable light, a_{max}^* is the maximum value of the chlorophyll specific phytoplankton absorption spectrum and $\phi_{\mu,max}$ is the quantum yield for growth.

In principle, the Morel model calculates gross primary production. However, since in Morel *et al.* (1996), the model produced values in close agreement with 24h *in situ* incubations it retrieves a value closer to net primary production. Following Morel *et al.* (1996) both $\phi_{\mu,max}$ and a_{max}^* are parameterised in terms of chlorophyll. The irradiance scaling factor, KPUR, is set to $80 \mu\text{mol quanta m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ at 20°C (this value leads to a P_{max}^B of $4.61 \text{gC (g Chl)}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ in the absence of photoinhibition; Morel *et al.*, 1996). KPUR (and hence P_{max}^B) is allowed to vary with temperature according to

$$\text{KPUR}(T) = \text{KPUR}(20) 1.065^{(T-20)}$$

For clarity, the Morel (1991) model updated with the Morel *et al.*, (1996) modifications is hereafter called the “LPCM model” after the Laboratoire de Physique et Chimie Marine, Villefranche-sur-mer, France. The operational implementation of the LPCM model as undertaken in PROOF within the framework of SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a, AVHRR-SST, irradiance and meteorological data, with specifications and assumptions noted below, is hereafter called the “*PROOF PP model*”; a graphical representation of this new framework is shown in Fig 8.1.

5.2.5 Modified LPCM Model: Effect of Non-Photosynthetic Pigments

The fourth satellite model considered in the project was developed at PML and is a modified form of the LPCM model using the approach of Babin *et al.* (1996) to estimate ϕ_m using the linear regression of mean daily PAR in the mixed layer against NPP and the inverse exponential of NPP against ϕ_m . The aim is to improve estimates of PP allowing for the considerable absorption by non-photosynthetic pigments (i.e. pigments that do not lead to organic growth) that are in abundance in low-latitude, high surface irradiance, regions.

6 BIOGEOCHEMICAL OCEAN MODELLING

6.1 Ocean model overview

In this section the DIADEM model including the physical model MICOM and the FDM02 ecosystem model is described. The “PROOF ocean model” is an evolution of the DIADEM model configuration, being based on the HYCOM physical ocean model, which is presented in Section 6.1.2. Finally the model run configuration is detailed.

6.1.1 The DIADEM model

6.1.1.1 MICOM

The Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM) is developed by Bleck and coworkers at the university of Miami, see e.g., *Bleck and Boudra (1986)*; *Bleck et al. (1989, 1992)*; *Smith et al. (1990)*. MICOM is characterized by the use of potential density as the vertical coordinate. This is possible since density is a monotonic function of depth. The motivation for using an isopycnic ocean model is that mixing along neutral surfaces, i.e. approximately surfaces of constant density, is several orders of magnitude larger than the mixing across density surfaces. Hence in MICOM the ocean is divided into a number of constant density layers where the density increases with depth. The interaction between the different layers is mostly through hydrostatic pressure forces, but also includes explicitly prescribed diapycnal mixing and convection processes. The isopycnic nature of the model allows for high resolution in areas with large density gradients, and artificial mixing only occurs along density surfaces where it is negligible compared to the prescribed eddy mixing.

The **upper layer is treated as a bulk mixed layer**, which allows for horizontal variations in the thermodynamic variables and density. It is based on an implementation of the Kraus-Turner mixed layer formulation (*Bleck et al., 1989*) and the formulation by *Gaspar et al. (1990)*. This allows the model to use realistic heat and freshwater fluxes and to interact with a dynamic and thermodynamic ice model.

The model solves the primitive equations consisting of the momentum equation for the velocity vector, a continuity equation for mass conservation or an isopycnic framework for layer thickness, two conservation equations for salt and heat and the hydrostatic equation relating pressure to depth (or in this case Montgomery potential to pressure).

The vertical coordinate in the model is the specific volume $\alpha = \rho^{-1}$, where ρ is the potential density with respect to sea level pressure. Using α , the horizontal momentum equation becomes:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t_\alpha} + \nabla_\alpha \frac{\mathbf{v}^2}{2} + (\zeta + f)\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{v} + \left(\dot{\alpha} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right) \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial p} + \nabla_\alpha M = -g \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\tau}}{\partial p} + \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right)^{-1} \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\nu_{mh} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \nabla_\alpha \mathbf{v} \right) \quad (6.1)$$

where $\mathbf{v} = (u; v)$ is the horizontal velocity vector, $\zeta = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x_\alpha} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y_\alpha}$ is the relative vorticity, f is the Coriolis parameter, $\alpha = \rho^{-1}$ is the specific volume, p is pressure, $M = gz + p\alpha$ is the Montgomery potential, gz is he geopotential, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the wind and bottom drag-induced shear stress and ν_{mh} is the variable momentum viscosity coefficient.

The continuity equation is given as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right) + \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\mathbf{v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\dot{\alpha} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right) = \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\nu_{hh} \nabla_\alpha \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right) \right), \quad (6.2)$$

where ν_{hh} is the thickness diffusion coefficient. $\dot{\rho} \frac{\partial z}{\partial \rho}$ is the generalized vertical velocity in isopycnic coordinates.

The conservation equations for heat and salt are given as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} T \right) + \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\mathbf{v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} T \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\dot{\alpha} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} T \right) = \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\nu \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \nabla_\alpha T \right) + \mathcal{H}_T, \quad (6.3)$$

where T represents any of the models thermodynamic variables, \mathcal{H}_T represent the sum of the diabatic source terms acting on T , and ν is the diffusion coefficient.

Finally, the hydrostatic equation is given as:

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial \alpha} = p. \quad (6.4)$$

The equation of state is the linear in salt (S) and cubic in temperature (T) according to *Friedrich and Levitus* (1972).

The model uses potential temperature and potential density. Under these conditions the compressibility effect is eliminated. The effect of the compressibility on the dynamics is negligible in most water masses, but in cold-water masses it becomes important.

In MICOM it is assumed that all model layers exist everywhere in the model domain. The thicknesses of the layers are entirely determined by the time evolving model equations and special transport algorithms are required to maintain positive thickness for the model layers at all times. The internal layers (below the upper mixed layer) will outcrop to the bathymetry and to the upper mixed layer, and they are therefore allowed to become massless with zero thickness. There are thermodynamic variables in all layers.

Vertical mixing processes include parameterizations for diapycnal mixing (transfer of salt and potential temperature between layers), convection (when the mixed layer water becomes denser than the isopycnal layers below) and entrainment/detrainment of mixed layer water (due to deepening/retreat of the mixed layer depth).

6.1.1.2 The biogeochemical model

The biochemical sub-module is described in *Drange* (1994), with extensions as in *Drange* (1996). The module was originally based on the chemical *Peng et al.* (1987) model, the seven-compartment ecosystem model by *Fasham et al.* (1990) and *Fasham* (1993) and the 3-dimensional extensions as described in *Sarmiento et al.* (1993). Some further improvements of the ecosystem model were done by *Drange* (1994, 1996), e.g., the bacteria equation was slightly reformulated to ensure a non-accumulating flow of nitrogen and carbon through the bacterial compartment. Also, equations for the evolution of total dissolved inorganic carbon and alkalinity were included, in addition to the seven compartments explicitly modelled in *Fasham et al.* (1990). Further, carbon based compartments of organic dissolved material and particulate matter were included explicitly in the model. In this formulation, the Redfield carbon to nitrogen ratios of DOC/DON and POC/PON are free floating and dependent on the flow of carbon and nitrogen through these compartments, as described by the model equations. The resulting model is hereafter referred to as the FDM02 model.

The basic equations evolving forward in time are the mass continuity equation, and the equations describing the transport of the biochemical model compartments. Continuity of mass for layer k in terms of layer thickness h_k reads

$$\frac{\partial h_k}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}_k h_k) - \nabla \cdot (K_h \nabla h_k) - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K_v \frac{\partial h_k}{\partial z} \right) = \left(\frac{\partial h_k}{\partial t} \right)_{diap}, \quad (6.5)$$

where t is the time, ∇r is the two-dimensional gradient operator, K_v and K_h are the diapycnal and isopycnal diffusion parameters and \mathbf{u}_k is the two-dimensional velocity vector, which is an input field from the ocean circulation model (MICOM). The isopycnal diffusivity K_h is kept fixed in the interior model domain, while the diapycnal diffusivity K_v is proportional to N_b^{-2} in the mixed layer and to N_b^{-1} in the layers below, where N_b is the local buoyancy frequency (*Drange, 1994*). The first term in (6.5) represents the local change of the layer thickness, the second describes the advection, the third and fourth are diffusive mixing terms in the isopycnal and diapycnal directions, respectively. The term on the right hand side of (6.5) describes the diapycnal exchange of mass. Further details may be obtained from *Drange (1994)*. The biochemical model compartments are evolving according to the transport equations;

$$\frac{\partial h_k C_k^i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}_k h_k C_k^i) - \nabla \cdot (K_h \nabla h_k C_k^i) - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K_v \frac{\partial h_k C_k^i}{\partial z} \right) = \left(\frac{\partial h_k C_k^i}{\partial t} \right)_{diap} + h_k \frac{\delta C_k^i}{\delta t}, \quad (6.6)$$

where C_k^i is compartment i in layer k . The first term in (6.6) is the local change of compartment i , while the second, third and fourth terms describe advection and diffusive mixing in the isopycnal and diapycnal directions, respectively. Further, the first term on the right hand side represents the exchange of matter across the isopycnal, while the second is a short hand notation for all the sources and sinks for compartment i . The last term in (6.6) indicates that the sources and sinks are evaluated locally; see *Drange (1994)* for a detailed description of the numerical implementations.

The following eleven compartments are explicitly modelled; phytoplankton (P), zooplankton (Z), bacteria (B), nitrate (N_n), ammonium (N_r), dissolved organic nitrogen -

DON (N_d), dissolved organic carbon - DOC (C_d), detritus as particulate organic nitrogen - PON (D_N), detritus as particulate organic carbon - POC (D_C), dissolved inorganic carbon - DIC (C_T) and alkalinity (A_T) (see Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1. A schematic representation of the photic zone biochemical system in the FDM02 model. Primary production is fuelled by nitrate (1) and ammonium (6), and reduced by phytoplankton exudation (4) and mortality (5). Zooplankton graze on phytoplankton (7), bacteria (12) and detritus (13) with prescribed efficiencies, and the fecal pellets represent a sink to detritus (14). Further, zooplankton losses (excretion, mortality, messy ingestion, Redfield balance term, grazing by higher predators, etc.) are split up as sinks to ammonium (11), dissolved organic matter (8) and an export term representing large sinking particles (9). The bacteria take up ammonium (17) and dissolved organic matter (18), and excrete ammonium (16). Particulate matter may sink (23) or may be broken down to dissolved matter (22). The concentration of dissolved inorganic carbon decreases during photosynthesis (3) and during formation of CaCO_3 (24), and increases during zooplankton and bacterial excretion (10, 19). Alkalinity increases during nitrate fuelled and decreases during ammonium fuelled primary production (2). Further, zooplankton and bacterial excretion increase the alkalinity (15, 21), while bacterial uptake of ammonium and the formation of CaCO_3 decrease A_T (20, 25).

Since nitrogen is generally regarded as the limiting nutrient for phytoplankton growth, nitrogen is used as the basis model currency. Also, as pointed out by *Fasham et al.* (1990), this allows us to partition the total primary production into new production fuelled by

nitrate, and regenerated production fuelled by ammonium. The nitrogen based compartments (P , Z , B , N_n , N_r , N_d , D_N) are given in terms of mmol N m^{-3} (millimoles of nitrogen per cubic meter) and the carbon based (C_d , D_C , C_T) in terms of mmol C m^{-3} (millimoles of carbon per cubic meter), respectively. The alkalinity A_T is expressed as charge equivalents meq m^{-3} (for ion X^q , where q is the charge, 1 mole corresponds to $|q|$ equivalents).

The photic or euphotic zone is normally defined as the zone in which there is a positive net primary production (see e.g. *Bearman et al.*, 1995). Thus, by definition the ecosystem cannot survive for long below the photic zone. In our formulation, the photic zone is defined as the penetration depth of 75% of the surface irradiance, but with a predefined minimum of 40 meter (*Drange*, 1994).

In the photic zone, the exchanges of nitrogen and carbon can be described by simple dynamical relations between the biochemical model compartments. The photic zone model is based on *Fasham et al.* (1990), with modifications as described in *Fasham* (1993) and *Drange* (1994, 1996). So-called Michaelis-Menten (M-M) type formulations are used to parameterize several of the processes (*Michaelis and Menten*, 1913), for which a maximum rate, usually constant or temperature dependent, is reduced by some hyperbolic unitless expression. See, e.g. *Goldberg et al.* (1977) or *Kremer and Nixon* (1978) for further comments on the M-M approach. The model equations and parameters can be found in *Drange* (1994), with the modifications described in *Drange* (1996).

At the base of the ecosystem, phytoplankton growth is controlled by the nutrients and the light available. It is assumed that the growth due to these two factors can be decoupled, and further that phytoplankton tends to prefer ammonium over nitrate as given by an exponential inhibition term acting on the latter. Phytoplankton losses include mortality, grazing by zooplankton and exudation. Zooplankton graze on phytoplankton, bacteria and particulate organic matter (detritus) according to corresponding grazing rates. Losses include mortality, excretion and “messy” ingestion. Note that the zooplankton compartment acts as a closure of the system, including predation by higher order organisms. The zooplankton losses are split up into three parts; one part is turned over to DON and one to ammonium, while the last part represents heavy particulate matter, which is immediately exported out of the photic zone. To maintain a constant carbon to nitrogen ratio for zooplankton, excess nitrogen is simply turned over to DON and excess carbon to DOC,

respectively. Bacteria are assumed to take up DON and ammonium; they are grazed by zooplankton and excrete DIC. Zooplankton graze on particulate organic matter. However, some of this is returned to POM through “sloppy” feeding and from zooplankton fecal pellets due to grazing on phytoplankton, bacteria and POM, respectively. Further, dead phytoplankton is a source for detritus, while some of the particulate matter break down to dissolved organic matter and some sink out of the photic zone. The particulate matter is subdivided into one nitrogen-based (PON) and one carbon-based (POC) pool, respectively. While phytoplankton, zooplankton and bacteria all have fixed Redfield nitrogen to carbon ratios; the corresponding ratio for particulate matter is governed by the flow of substance through the PON and POC compartments according to the model dynamics. A similar partitioning into DON and DOC is used for the description of dissolved matter. It is assumed that phytoplankton is the only compartment capable of fixing dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC). In addition, DIC is also lost during formation of calcium carbonate $CaCO_3$, while bacterial and zooplankton excretion lead to increased carbon concentrations. The CO_2 gas exchange at the air-water boundary, as well as adjustments due to evaporation and precipitation, also affect the DIC budget. It is assumed that the relative composition of salts do not change with salinity. (see *Drange* (1994) for details). Biological uptake of NO_3^- and NH_4^+ results in an increase of the alkalinity for the former and a reduction for the latter, respectively. In addition, the alkalinity decreases whenever calcium carbonate is produced.

A nutrient regeneration model is used below the photic zone. To be more specific, the phytoplankton, zooplankton, bacteria and DON compartments decay to ammonium and then to nitrate, and DOC decays to DIC. For all these processes, a constant (and identical) decay rate is used. A remineralization of the POM to ammonium is assumed. See *Drange* (1994, 1996) for further details.

6.1.2 The PROOF ocean model

The requirements for the vertical discretization in ocean circulation models and models for the marine biogeochemistry generally differ. For example, while the circulation models often treat the surface ocean as a bulk mixed layer (such as MICOM), this is not optimal for the marine ecosystem module. Phytoplankton growth is dependent on the energy from the sunlight, and the primary production is therefore confined to the few uppermost tens of metres in the ocean. Thus, choosing the vertical discretization is not straightforward for a

coupled physical-biochemical ocean model system. One example is the use of density as the dependent vertical coordinate, i.e., an isopycnic discretization. Drange (1994) realized the above problems when coupling a biochemical model to the isopycnic coordinate MICOM model, and introduced a layer sub-split procedure, i.e., to ensure a finer vertical resolution for the ecosystem in the physical mixed layer. This worked well, but made the source code relatively complicated, as it has been applied in the DIADEM configuration.

A recent improvement of the MICOM model has been the introduction of a hybrid vertical coordinate. The new HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) was first presented by Bleck (2002), and introduces a very flexible way of tuning the vertical discretization for a desired purpose. For example, the model uses ordinary z-layers in the physical mixed layer, and with a smooth transition it goes over to isopycnic coordinates in the deep ocean. This is appropriate also for a biochemical model, as long as the number of z-layers is sufficient for resolving the biochemical dynamics in the physical mixed layer.

For the above reasons, the model run in PROOF was a new 3-D model, coupling the ecosystem described in section 6.1.1.2 to HYCOM.

6.1.3 Configuration of the PROOF ocean model simulations

An orthogonal curvilinear grid with a pronounced resolution in the Northwest Atlantic is used in the present PROOF ocean model. The model grids include the North Atlantic and the Arctic. The resolution is enhanced in the Nordic Seas while a high resolution is still retained in the Seas off Europe. Thus a proper representation of the inflow of Atlantic water, with its temperature, salinity and content of nutrients, from the Gulf Stream can be maintained without introducing complicated nesting procedures. The use of a variable model resolution and a large model domain allow us to apply “closed” boundaries far from the area of interest where a relaxation to climatology is applied.

The model grid has a resolution of about 12.5 km resolution in the Celtic Sea and North Sea, see Figure 6.2. The model has 22 vertical layers. The following density values have been considered in the isopycnic layers (from the upper layer to the lower layer):

Layer Sigma-Theta:

1=21.800 2=22.200 3=22.600 4=23.050 5=23.550 6=24.050 7=24.960 8=25.680
9=26.250 10=26.690 11=27.030 12=27.290 13=27.490 14=27.660 15=27.800 16=27.900
17=27.970 18=28.020 19=28.050 20=28.080 21=28.100 22=28.110

Figure 6.2. The orthogonal curvilinear grid giving a typical resolution of 10 km over the Celtic Sea region

The model is forced by atmospheric data from ECMWF, which is available on an approximately 1 by 1 degree grid and with 6 hourly resolution. This includes full thermodynamic forcing with computation of heat and freshwater fluxes in addition to the transfer of wind stress. The atmospheric fluxes are computed from air temperature, relative humidity, dew-point temperature, cloud cover, precipitation, and mean sea-level pressure. The wind stresses are derived from the atmospheric wind data.

6.2 PROOF Ocean model simulation results

This section contains results of the PROOF ocean model simulations based on the coupled HYCOM-ecosystem model, using the FDM02 formulation for describing the ecosystem.

The model system was set up for the North Atlantic using the orthogonal curvilinear grid shown in Figure 6.2. Note that the poles have been mapped to new locations, i.e., to

increase the grid resolution in the North Atlantic. The model uses a relaxation scheme (towards climatology) at the various open ocean boundaries, i.e., in the South Atlantic, the Mediterranean, the Baltic Sea and the Hudson Bay. The connection to the Pacific Ocean has also been shut off by closing the Bering Strait.

The HYCOM restart file was taken from other simulations within the TO^PAZ project, while we use very simple initial conditions for the biochemistry. To be more specific, the following surface values were defined: $P = 0.14 \text{ mmol N m}^3$, $Z = B = 0.014 \text{ mmol N m}^3$, $N_r = N_d = D_N = 0.1 \text{ mmol N m}^3$ and $C_d = D_C = 0.1 \text{ mmol C m}^3$. The carbon based initial values have been calculated from the corresponding nitrogen based, using the Redfield carbon to nitrogen ratio of phytoplankton. Thus, the free floating DON/DOC and PON/POC ratios are initialized using the corresponding ratio of phytoplankton. At greater depths, the phytoplankton, zooplankton, bacteria, ammonium, DON and DOC compartments are assumed to decrease exponentially according to a characteristic layer index of 10.

The presentation given here will be limited to include the first few months of the model evolution. Since the biochemical model will need 2–3 years to enter a stable cycle, the results will only provide a first qualitative assessment of the dynamical behaviour of the ecosystem.

We start by showing the surface distribution of phytoplankton and the current pattern in the Gulf Stream region for day 105 in 1997 in Figure 6.3. Three large scale eddies can be observed, and it can be seen how characteristic Gulf Stream rings are formed by advecting phytoplankton into these eddies. The new advection scheme developed at NERSC by Y. Morel and coworkers provides smooth and realistic fields, which could be seen in corresponding plots using the standard HYCOM advection scheme. It should be mentioned that the current model grid resolution is not strictly eddy resolving, and thus a detailed study of eddy circulation features would require higher spatial resolution.

Figure 6.4 shows surface layer concentrations of phytoplankton for the initial time (1997 day 0) and at the days 7, 28, 63, 91 and 119, respectively. A large “artificial” bloom is triggered by the model in the South Atlantic. The reason for this is probably because the initial ecosystem (i.e., the initial conditions) is not well balanced. That is, allowing phytoplankton to exist initially under such favourable light and nutrient conditions triggers an immediate bloom. However, the artificial bloom soon collapses, and the model enters a more realistic cycle. A positive result is that a realistic (at least qualitatively) North Atlantic

spring bloom of phytoplankton evolves northwards, reaching the Nordic Seas in the end of March/ beginning of April.

Figure 6.3. The figure shows the surface distribution of phytoplankton [$\text{mmol N} \text{ m}^{-3}$] and the current pattern in the Gulf Stream for day 105 in 1997. Three large scale eddies can be observed; note especially how phytoplankton rich water near the coast is advected into them, initiating the formation of so-called Gulf Stream rings (the current grid resolution is not fully eddy-resolving, i.e., higher resolution should be used for a detailed study of the eddies). The advection scheme used in the experiment is new and has been developed by Y. Morel and co-workers at NERSC, and it produces very smooth fields compared to the standard HYCOM approach.

Figure 6.5 shows the corresponding concentrations of zooplankton. As expected, the phytoplankton blooms are closely followed by corresponding zooplankton blooms, which occur a little later since they need the phytoplankton to grow.

Depth profiles of phytoplankton for a section at 40-N are shown in Figure 6.6. It is seen that the too large concentrations of phytoplankton in the deep ocean specified initially disappear after a few weeks. Later, the North Atlantic spring bloom can be seen in the few

uppermost layers of the model, starting in the west and moving slowly towards the east of the basin.

Figure 6.4. Surface layer concentrations of phytoplankton [mmol N m^{-3}]. The specified initial value (day 0 in 1997) is shown in the top left plot, followed by the concentrations for day 7 (top, right), day 28 (middle, left), day 63 (middle, right), day 91 (bottom, left) and day 119 (bottom, right), respectively. It is interesting to see how fast the model responds to the initial distributions in the South Atlantic, where an "artificial" large bloom is seen after only 7 days. Then, the situation settles down, before a North Atlantic spring bloom starts near the North African coast, and then spreading northwards reaching the Nordic Seas around day 100.

Figure 6.5. Surface layer concentrations of zooplankton [mmol N m^{-3}]. The specified initial value (day-0 in 1997) is shown in the top left plot, followed by the concentrations for day 7 (top, right), day 28 (middle, left), day 63 (middle, right), day 91 (bottom, left) and day 119 (bottom, right), respectively. It is seen that the phytoplankton spring bloom is followed by a little later zooplankton bloom, as expected since the zooplankton grows on the primary producers.

Figure 6.6. Depth profiles of phytoplankton for a 40°N section. The top left plot shows the initial distribution (day 0 in 1997), then followed by the situation for the days 7 (row 1 column 2), 14 (r1 c3), 21 (r2 c1), 77 (r2 c2), 84 (r2 c3), 91 (r3 c1), 98 (r3 c2), 105 (r3 c3) and 112 (r4 c2), respectively. During the first three weeks, deep phytoplankton concentrations set initially disappear. Later, a bloom is seen in the few uppermost layers, starting in the middle of March.

7 VALIDATION OF MODELS AND ALGORITHMS

7.1 Regional validation against *in situ* measurements

7.1.1 Upwelling region off northwest Spain

7.1.1.1 Introduction

A comprehensive programme of field measurements, part funded by the European Commission, was undertaken during the OMEX II phase II experiment off the northwest coast of Spain in 1997-2000 (contract number MAS3-CT97-0076). In OMEX II-II only a simple empirical model was available for satellite-*in situ* comparison; the semi-analytical algorithm implemented within PROOF was used with these *in situ* data to perform a regional comparison (Joint *et al.*, 2002).

7.1.1.2 Methods

The methodology of the *in situ* sampling is explained in Joint *et al.*, (2002) and the paper is attached as an appendix to D3. For the PROOF PP model inputs were: 1) the *in situ* measured surface chlorophyll, with the assumption of a homogeneous vertical distribution, to mirror what can be measured from satellite; 2) the sea-surface temperature; 3) the surface irradiance obtained from the ECMWF fields of cloud and 4) the local ambient pressure, humidity, ozone, precipitable water and wind speed extracted from SeaWiFS ancillary data.

7.1.1.3 Results

Fig. 7.1, adapted from Joint *et al.* (2002), shows a scatter plot of estimates of primary production using the PROOF PP model and all the field measurements. Note that the data from IIM in January 1998 have been re-analysed using the spectral approach of Kyewalyanga *et al.* (1992) as opposed to the broad-band approach (Platt *et al.*, 1980); also see discussion in Tilstone *et al.* (2003). This is because, arguably, a spectral approach gives a more accurate

Figure 7.1. Comparison of primary production estimated by the PROOF primary production model with field data obtained during the OMEX II-II project by PML in March 1998, August 1998, by ULB in June 1997, July 1998 and September 1999 and by IIM in January 1998. The solid line indicates the 1:1 relationship and the envelope shows the 1:1 line \pm 100%

estimate of gross primary production. It has the result of improving the fit with the model for these winter, low production estimates.

The line shows the 1:1 relationship and the envelope is $\pm 0.3\log_{10}PP$ (as plotted by Berthon and Morel, 1992), that is, a 100% overestimate or 50% underestimate. It is clear that the semi-analytical model gives estimates of production, which are close to the measured production over a very wide range of values, from low winter to high upwelling production even with the assumption of uniform chlorophyll with depth. The spread of data is slightly less than that noted by Berthon and Morel (1992) who presented an earlier validation of the Morel (1991) model.

7.1.2 Celtic Sea and western English Channel

7.1.2.1 Introduction

The second of the two regional comparison areas was the western English Channel and Celtic Sea. The regions have been well studied over many years with *in situ* measurements of primary production and satellite observations of phytoplankton and sea-surface temperature. Briefly, the region is characterised by seasonal stratification in the northern part of the western English Channel and the Celtic Sea with well-mixed water persisting on the French side of the Channel. The stratified and well mixed waters are separated by temperature fronts (e.g. Ushant front around the Brittany Peninsula); during Spring and Summer a front also forms between the Celtic Sea stratified and shelf edge waters where breaking internal waves cause a persistent cooling.

7.1.2.2 Methods

Project specific data were obtained for the validation of the PROOF primary production algorithm in both the Celtic Sea and the western English Channel.

In the Celtic Sea a cruise was undertaken on *RRS Discovery* from 17 – 28 May 2000 and involved a total of 11 days of sampling. The methodology is given in full detail in Woods *et al.*, submitted, (paper attached as an appendix to D4), and only briefly described herein. The positions of the stations are shown in Fig. 7.2. Initially, four stations (A, B, C and D) in St. George's Channel were each occupied for 24 hours in regions where mixed or frontal conditions were expected to develop. Three stations, which experience seasonal stratification (E, F and G) were sampled from 22 to 28 May 2000 to the south of the front. At station G, experiments were done over a 72h period (22 to 24 May) and at both stations E and F, sampling took place over 48 h periods (25 to 26 May and 27 to 28 May respectively).

Figure 7.2. AVHRR image of the Celtic Sea showing sea surface temperature (SST) on 8 April with station positions overlaid (from Woods et al., submitted)

Measurements of primary production were taken using the ^{14}C method and a fast repetition rate fluorometer (FRRF: Kolber and Falkowski, 1993). Note, the FRRF work was undertaken as part of separate research project and does not form part of, nor is a deliverable within, the PROOF project: the data are included herein purely for comparison purposes.

In the western English Channel, water samples were obtained approximately weekly at station L4 during 2001 (see Fig. 7.3) and brought back to the laboratory. The full methodology is given in Woods (2003: PhD thesis attached as an appendix to D4); briefly, primary production was measured by placing samples inoculated with ^{14}C in a light gradient and with a laboratory-based FRRF.

Figure 7.3. SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a image for 4 June 2001 showing location of the L4 sampling site south of Rame Head.

The performances of the LPCM and VGPM models were assessed using the data from station L4 in 2001 and for the stations of the Celtic Sea cruise in May 2000. The satellite models were parameterised with *in situ* measured chlorophyll in order that their performance could be attributed directly to the model and not complicated by uncertainties in chlorophyll retrieval from satellite. To investigate the influence of different parameters and aid understanding of model performance the models were run a number of times using different combinations of modelled and measured parameters. For the LPCM model, the parameters changed were K_{PAR} (attenuation coefficient of PAR), Z_{eu} (euphotic depth) and $KPUR$ (the irradiance scaling factor). For the VGPM model, the factors changed were $P^{B_{opt}}$ (that was replaced with measured P^B_m) and the variable euphotic depth (which was replaced with the assumption of a fixed depth of 30m). Estimates of PAR at the surface were calculated using Gregg and Carder (1990). The PAR model was run assuming no cloud cover so PAR was calculated simply as a function of Julian day and latitude, but with standard atmospheric scattering and absorption parameters.

The results presented herein are the model runs in their “standard form” (i.e. with purely modelled parameters) so as to most appropriately compare with operation with satellite data. Full descriptions of results including comparisons with models runs with various modified inputs are shown in Woods (2003), Ph.D. Thesis submitted as appendix to D4.

7.1.2.3 Results

7.1.2.3.1 Temporal variability of daily primary production at L4 and the Celtic Sea

Figure 7.4 shows the temporal variability in the measured and modelled data in the Celtic Sea during the May 2000 cruise and at L4 during 2001. As can be seen the L4 series provides comprehensive sampling at one location throughout the year.

Figure 7.4. Daily, depth-integrated primary production a) in the Celtic Sea and b) at L4 where satellite models were run in their default modes ^{14}C (●), FRRF (▲), VGPM model (■) and LPCM model (◆). All data were integrated over the top 30m of the water column.

7.1.2.3.2 PP_{Daily} from LPCM model

Comparisons between the LPCM model and *in situ* FRRF or ^{14}C production estimates in the Celtic Sea and L4 are shown in Figures 7.5 and 7.6 and the regression statistics are given in Table 7.1. In general the modelled and measured estimates had similar magnitudes with the exception of the ^{14}C production at L4. The LPCM model explained, respectively, 12% and 47% of the variance in ^{14}C production estimates and 53% and 83% respectively in FRRF production estimates. It can be seen that the L4 LPCM/FRRF data lie very close to the 1:1 line and if the regression is forced through the origin then the variance explained

falls to 67% but the slope changes to 0.99. Similarly, with the Celtic Sea LPCM/FRRF forcing the regression through the origin gives a slope of 1.0. The standard error at L4 is relatively high at 431 and 244 mgC m⁻²day⁻¹ for 14C and FRRF respectively and somewhat lower in the Celtic Sea data at 146 and 106 mgCm⁻²day⁻¹ respectively.

In the case of the ¹⁴C estimates for L4 the regression was biased by two, high production points: if these are removed the variance explained falls to 41% and the slope increases significantly (1.52 compared to 0.64). The overestimate may be partly explained by the attenuation of light: the K_{PAR} algorithm used in the LPCM model was designed for Case I waters and was based on measured chlorophyll concentrations and published descriptions of the spectral attenuation of light by chlorophyll and water. In Case I waters, the non-linear effect of phytoplankton pigments are reasonably well described by models (Morel, 1988) but the absorption by non-biological particles is not accounted for in the LPCM model. In the Celtic Sea, the sites sampled were relatively far from terrestrial input and the modelled K_{PAR} estimates were generally higher than the measured values. However, the L4 site is case 2 during the winter and early spring and may be considered as intermediate case 1/case 2 throughout the rest of the year.

Table 1. Regressions statistics for the LPCM model compared to ¹⁴C or FRRF data for each area.

Area	<i>In situ</i> data	slope	intercept	R ²	Std Err.
Celtic	14C	0.24	409	0.12	146
Celtic	FRRF	0.56	261	0.53	106
L4	14C	0.64	614	0.47	431
L4	FRRF	0.75	337	0.83	244

Figure 7.5. Plots of daily depth integrated primary production from the LPCM model against that derived from ¹⁴C and FRRF approaches: for the Celtic Sea. The 1:1 lines are shown.

Figure 7.6. Plots of daily depth integrated primary production from the LPCM model against that derived from ¹⁴C and FRRF approaches for L4. The 1:1 lines are shown.

7.1.2.3.3 PP_{Daily} from VGPM model

The VGPM model, as can be seen from Fig. 7.7 and 7.8, and the regression statistics in Table 7.2, always significantly overestimated production compared to ¹⁴C and FRRF estimates in both the Celtic Sea and at L4. The model explained 11% and 47% of variance when compared to the Celtic Sea ¹⁴C and FRRF data and 76% and 32% of variance of the ¹⁴C and FRRF data at L4. In all cases the standard error is significantly higher than with the LPCM model.

The way by which algal physiology is included in the VGPM and LPCM models were different. Behrenfeld and Falkowski (1997a) noted that the P_{opt}^B factor in their model is responsible for most of the unexplained variability observed in the model results. P_{opt}^B is regulated mainly by P_{max}^B , itself determined by the enzymatically controlled Calvin cycle

and, therefore, by temperature (Behrenfeld and Falkowski, 1997a). The high order polynomial model used to calculate P_{opt}^B as a function of temperature is described as only a preliminary model but is easy to implement as temperature is a variable that can be remotely sensed and is theoretically a good indicator of potential productivity given no other limiting conditions. P_{opt}^B was found to be much higher than measured P_{max}^B values. In the Celtic Sea, the low range of temperatures led to very consistent values of P_{opt}^B over the study, whilst for L4 the dependence on temperature was clear and P_{opt}^B increased over the summer with water temperature.

Table 2. Regressions statistics for the VGPM model compared to ^{14}C or FRRF data for each area.

Area	<i>In situ</i> data	slope	intercept	R ²	Std Err.
Celtic	^{14}C	1.05	1339	0.11	644
Celtic	FRRF	2.28	757	0.47	500
L4	^{14}C	2.37	457	0.76	934
L4	FRRF	1.37	1585	0.32	1554

Figure 7.7. Plots of daily depth integrated primary production from the VGPM model against that derived from a) ¹⁴C and b) FRRF approaches for the Celtic Sea. The 1:1 lines are shown.

Figure 7.8. Plots of daily depth integrated primary production from the VGPM model against that derived from a) ¹⁴C and b) FRRF approaches for L4. The 1:1 lines are shown

A large proportion of the variance in the modelled production was explained by that in chlorophyll (67%) and euphotic depth (61%) and 76% of the variance was explained by the product of the two. Variance in P_{opt}^B only explained 37% of that in modelled production.

7.1.3 Conclusions

Results from the LPCM model, in its standard mode, showed good agreement with those from the ¹⁴C and FRRF techniques in both a research cruise covering a number of different physical environments in the Celtic Sea and over the period of a year in one location, L4, in the western English Channel. The best comparisons were seen between the LPCM model and the estimates from the FRRF. For L4 data, 83% of the variance was

explained by the regression of production estimates from the model against those from the FRRF and the slope of the line was 0.75.

Comparison with *in situ* data for the upwelling region off northwest Spain similarly confirmed that the LPCM model gives good retrievals over a wide range of primary production at different times of the year. These results suggest that the model we have selected for PROOF is appropriate for regional estimation of primary production.

In the western English Channel and Celtic Sea comparisons the VGPM model gave estimates twice as high as either the LPCM model or the ^{14}C or FRRF approaches and all the data points lie above the 1:1 line. Hence, this model was confirmed as unsuitable for use in the European shelf seas under consideration in its current form with $P_{\text{opt}}^{\text{B}}$ parameterised in terms of purely SST.

7.2 Basin-scale validation against *in situ* measurements

In order to test the PROOF primary production algorithm over basin scales two approaches have been attempted. The first, as noted in the Description of Work, is to make use of a data set obtained prior to the PROOF project over a long transect from Cape Town to the UK that covers a number of different “provinces” (Longhurst, 1998). However, such large basin-scale datasets are very expensive to compile, and are limited spatially and temporally; hence, this kind of comparison suffers from the statistical limitations of sparse datasets. Therefore a second approach was also undertaken wherein results from the PROOF PP model were compared with outputs from a number of models operated worldwide provided with a common set of input variables. It should be stressed that this activity is not a formal PROOF deliverable: indeed, the Primary Production Algorithm Round Robin 3 (PPARR3) had not started when PROOF was proposed. However, it is instructive to compare the results of the PROOF work with results from leaders in the field (such as Behrenfeld, Morel, Esaias, Marra and Bidigare). The comparison with other models is presented in section 8.2.

7.2.1 Comparison with AMT-6 Data

7.2.1.1 Introduction

The 6th Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT-6) was conducted along a meridional transect (32°S to 48°N) through the eastern Atlantic Ocean on board *RRS James Clark Ross*

on passage between Cape Town, South Africa and Grimsby, UK from 15 May to 16 June 1998 (Fig. 7.9). As can be seen the track covers a wide range of “provinces” from oligotrophic gyres to eutrophic waters in the Benguela upwelling west of southern Africa. Hence, the cruise provides an excellent opportunity to test the spatial, and trophic capability of the PROOF PP model.

Figure 7.9. AMT-6 track superimposed on a) SeaWiFS mean chlorophyll and b) AVHRR mean SST for the eastern Atlantic, May 1998. The provinces are: BENG: Benguela Current Coastal Province; ETRA: Eastern Tropical Atlantic Province; CNRY: Eastern (Canary) Coastal Province; NAST-E: North Atlantic Subtropical Gyre Province; and NADR: North Atlantic Drift Province.

7.2.1.2 Methods

The methodology of the sampling programme is described in detail in Tilstone *et al.*, submitted (paper attached as an appendix to D4) and only briefly described herein. A total of 24 stations were sampled (one a day between 08:00 and 09:00 GMT) at approximately 320 km intervals along the track. Simultaneous primary production and bio-optical measurements were made at 14 stations. Four methods were used to calculate primary production:

- i. *In situ simulated ($\Sigma PP_{(6h)}$) method*
- ii. *Broad band photosynthesis–irradiance(PE) method*
- iii. *Spectral photosynthesis–irradiance(PE) method using the phytoplankton absorption spectra ($a_{ph}(\lambda)$): $\Sigma PP_{(PUR\ aph)}$*
- iv. *Spectral photosynthesis–irradiance(PE) method using the photosynthetic absorption spectra($a_{ps}(\lambda)$)*

For the purposes of this report the primary production calculated using the spectral PE-method (iii above) was the standard to compare with the satellite algorithms.

In Tilstone *et al.* , submitted, the *in situ* primary production was compared with four satellite algorithms:

- i. An empirical model relating $\log \Sigma PP$ to $\log \text{Chl}$ (Behrenfeld *et al.*, 1998) which had previously been used in the OMEXII-II programme
- ii. The LPCM model
- iii. The VGPM model
- iv. The LPCM model modified following the approach of Babin *et al.*, (1996) to estimate ϕ_m using the linear regression of mean daily PAR in the mixed layer against NPP and the inverse exponential of NPP against ϕ_m .

For the purposes of this validation only model ii and iii are considered.

7.2.1.3 Results

Log-log model II regression, percentage of variance explained and root mean square error (RMS) for the two satellite algorithms plotted against $\Sigma PP_{(PUR\ aph)}$ are given in Fig 7.10 Primary production calculated using the LPCM model had a slope closer to 1, under estimated ΣPP by only 7 %, explained 61 % of the variance and had the lowest rms error (0.69) indicating that this algorithm gives the best retrieval accuracy for integrated primary

production over the eastern Atlantic basin. When one point was removed (dark triangle; Fig 7.10) the percentage variance explained increased to 68 % and rms decreased to 0.45. By comparison, primary production calculated with the VGPM using P_{opt}^B derived from SST explained the highest percentage variance (63 %) with rms error (0.72) and under estimated ΣPP by 18 %. Deviation from the 1:1 line, was caused by an over estimation of ΣPP in the eutrophic provinces of the Benguela Current Coastal Province and the NADR.

Figure 7.10. Comparison of satellite derived primary production for the eastern Atlantic basin using model II regression of a) LPCM and b) VGPM models plotted against $\Sigma PP_{(PUR_{aph})}$.

7.3 Sensitivity Analysis

To assess the variables that have the greatest influence on the computation of satellite-derived ΣPP , a sensitivity analysis was performed based on the in situ data obtained during the AMT6 cruise. Each variable used to compute ΣPP was fixed at its mean and ΣPP was re-computed by varying it through its observed maximum and minimum during the cruise. The results are summarised as box plots in Fig 7.11, with a total mean error given below each plot which indicates the degree a variable influences the computation of ΣPP ; the higher the error the greater the influence.

For all satellite models C_{insitu} was the variable that most affected the calculation of primary production and the other variables showed lesser effects. For ΣPP calculated with the Behrenfeld and Falkowski (1997a) VGPM model ($\Sigma PP_{(BF97)}$), C_{insitu} and Z_{eu} had the

greatest influence. For the LPCM model, C_{insitu} and ϕ_m exhibited the greatest effect. In both of these models, Z_{eu} and ϕ_m were derived from C_{insitu} , which accounts for the high influence on the computation of ΣPP .

Figure 7.11. Sensitivity analysis to assess the degree to which satellite algorithm variables affect the calculation of primary production (a.) in the VGPM model $\Sigma PP_{(BF97)}$ and (b.) the LPCM model $\Sigma PP_{(M91)}$. The boundary of the box indicates the 25th and 75th percentile, the line within the box indicates the median, the whiskers above and below the box indicate the 90th and 10th percentiles and the dots outside the box are outlying points. The numbers given at the bottom of the plots are the mean errors incurred in calculating ΣPP .

8 PROOF RESULTS

8.1 *An operational primary production system*

In PROOF integrated primary production is estimated operationally using the LPCM model with inputs of daily satellite-derived chlorophyll and daily meteorological data and model output and weekly sea surface temperature (SST) data; it should be stressed that no climatological-mean data are involved in these calculations. Chlorophyll is extracted from SeaWiFS imagery (at 18 or 9 km resolution). Chlorophyll in the model is assumed to be constant with depth and equal to that retrieved from SeaWiFS data; *i.e.* $C(z) = C_{\text{sat}}$, hence no account is made of possible sub-surface chlorophyll maxima. However, sub-surface chlorophyll maxima are not necessarily sub-surface primary production maxima (e.g. see Joint *et al.*, 2002, Figure 3), or may be the result of higher chlorophyll to carbon ratios (e.g. Taylor *et al.*, 1997). SST is extracted from NOAA MCSST fields (McClain *et al.*, 1985) and used to calculate *KPUR* as a function of SST. The PROOF implementation assumes that temperature is constant with depth and equal to SST.

In order to quantify the effect of using satellite derived values to force the model, with the assumption of no variation with depth, a seasonal cycle of *in situ* vertical chlorophyll and temperature values from a stratified station in the North Sea (Allen *et al.*, 2001) was used with the PROOF PP model to estimate primary production. This station may be considered typical of the shelf stratified water found over much of the European continental shelf. The effect of assuming temperature is constant with depth (and equal to SST) was relatively small with a maximum overestimation of primary production integrated to the euphotic depth (1% light level) of 3.7% in late Summer but with typical errors <1.5% and zero during winter and late autumn when the euphotic depth is within the mixed layer (*i.e.* with homogeneous temperature). In other cases the euphotic depth may be below the thermocline and in these deeper levels production will be slightly overestimated (through the effect of assuming a higher temperature); however, since the deeper layers will typically have lower production due to attenuation of light, the error on integrated production is small. These results confirm the findings of Bricaud *et al.* (2002) who investigated the

effect of SST on the LPCM model in the Mediterranean Sea: they found that temperature has only a second order effect on production.

Assuming chlorophyll is constant with depth and equal to the satellite derived values induces greater errors: using the North Sea data set the integrated production had an average error of ~8% but with maximum overestimation by 28% and underestimation by 16%. Overestimation occurred when chlorophyll was high at the surface falling to low values at the thermocline; conversely, underestimation occurred with chlorophyll maxima at depth. Interestingly, assuming the North Sea data are representative of a seasonal cycle, the total annual production was overestimated by only 1.5%, suggesting that applications utilising yearly production will not be affected by ignoring vertical structure.

For regional usage of the model, daily SeaWiFS imagery at 9 km (or 1.1km) and weekly MCSST data are used; the above-surface, downwelling light field is computed using the model of Gregg and Carder (1990) with input variables of wind speed (derived from model fields from the US National Centers for Environmental Prediction, NCEP) and ozone concentration (from EP-TOMS). Cloud has a large effect on the irradiance reaching the sea surface so it is important to correct irradiance estimates for the degree of daily cloud cover over the region. This is calculated using the approach used by Antoine and Morel (1996), with cloud cover derived from ECMWF fields. When no chlorophyll data can be derived from SeaWiFS for a particular day, primary production is calculated using chlorophyll values from the previous non-zero data but with the meteorological data for that day. The approach has already been used in one of the PROOF areas (Galician Sea) and results have been published (see Joint *et al.*, 2002).

For basin scale estimates of primary production (see Fig 8.1) the model inputs were monthly global fields of SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a (O'Reilly *et al.*, 1998), SST (from Pathfinder) and SeaWiFS derived Photosynthetically Available Radiation (PAR) Frouin *et al.* (2002) at 18 km resolution (2048 x 1024 pixels). The PAR fields are in units of mol photon m⁻² d⁻¹, i.e., the daily integrated PAR and obviously include the effects of cloud and atmospheric absorption. However the model requires hourly spectrally resolved irradiance, which was calculated as follows. First, the daylength is found for each month and 18 km latitude bin from a look-up-table (dimensions 1024 x 12). Using equations 2.6 and 2.7 in Kirk (2000) the daily integrated PAR and daylength were used to calculate hourly instantaneous PAR at each pixel (the equations assume a sinusoidal profile of irradiance).

To provide the spectral variability a LUT of values was constructed using a run of the Gregg and Carder (1990) spectral solar irradiance model for noon on serial day 181 at latitude 50° N. The integrated irradiance (PAR) equalled 1695 $\mu\text{mol quanta m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Finally, the hourly instantaneous PAR for each pixel was divided by this value and the ratio used to scale the spectrally resolved LUT for each pixel for each time interval.

Figure 8.1. Implementation of the PROOF PP model for global estimation of primary production.

The limitations of the model are that no information on solar angle is included and would affect the air-sea transmission of light; the spectral LUT was run for a clear sky and cloudy skies may give a different spectral response: this is very hard to model.

8.2 Results from the operational system

8.2.1 Regional results: seasonal variability in the effect of wind induced upwelling off northwest Spain

The west coast of Spain and Portugal is characterised by periods of intense upwelling, which are driven by northerly winds. Upwelling occurs frequently throughout the year and especially in the summer months (Wooster *et al.*, 1976; Smyth *et al.*, 2001) and is interspersed with relaxation periods. The upwelling periods are variable in time, but generally last for about 2 weeks (Moncoiffe *et al.*, 2000). As a consequence of these frequent upwelling events, the coastal seas of the N.W. Iberian Peninsula are extremely productive and the Rias of Galicia support one of the most intensive shellfish farming industries in Europe (Tenore *et al.*, 1995). Therefore, the Spanish upwelling region is an excellent example for PROOF of a high productivity coastal/shelf region with an economically important fishery.

As mentioned in section 7.2.1 the upwelling region off Spain was the focus of project, called OMEXII-II, part funded by the EU between 1997 and 2000 wherein extensive in situ measurements of primary production and a wide range of other physical, chemical, biological and physical data were obtained. Since the synthesis paper on primary production including satellite algorithms was re-submitted, following initial referees comments, in October 2001 (some 18 months into PROOF) it provided an excellent opportunity to update the manuscript, extend the satellite time series (to the end of 2000) and test the prototype regional primary production algorithm (Joint *et al.*, 2002).

Figure 8.2 shows a SeaWiFS image for 15 August 2000, which has been processed to give estimates of chlorophyll concentration (Lavender and Groom, 1999). A number of features are apparent. Ekman upwelling results in increased chlorophyll concentrations along the shelf edge and this image gives a good visual indication of the geographical scale of elevated chlorophyll concentrations at the Iberian margin. A number of off-shore filaments are visible, with enhanced chlorophyll concentrations penetrating into the deep ocean. Images like this suggest that some of the phytoplankton produced on the shelf and at the shelf break as a result of upwelling, is transported into the deep ocean in filaments. Fig. 8.2 also gives a good indication of the heterogeneity in the surface chlorophyll distributions in this region.

Figure 8.2. Full resolution (1.1 km) SeaWiFS image of surface chlorophyll concentration on 15 August 2000 showing the heterogeneity of chlorophyll distribution on the shelf and elevated chlorophyll concentrations in off-shore filaments extending into the open ocean. The 200m and 2000m depth contours are indicated. The upper inset shows the three regions used in the analysis — coast, slope and open-ocean. The lower inset is the 9 km daily composite corresponding to the main figure; this is the resolution used in the data analysis.

The model was applied to daily 9-km chlorophyll data extracted from the three regions in the upper inset in Fig 8.2 and the monthly averaged production is shown in Fig 8.3. There are significant differences in seasonal patterns of productivity in the different regions and in the 3 years of the analysis. On the shelf, highest primary production occurred in the summer months but in the open ocean there was evidence for spring maxima. The timing of these production maxima varied between the 3 years. In 1998, highest production in the open ocean was in May but in 1999 it was in April and in 2000, it occurred in March. There were similar changes in the timing of the maximum primary production rate on the shelf; in 1998, the highest monthly production was in August, in 1999 it occurred in June and in 2000 it was again in August. As would be expected, the primary production on the shelf was higher than the slope, which was higher than the open ocean in every month.

These data allow the calculation of annual primary production rates for the three regions under consideration: the primary production of the shelf varied between 334 and 301 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, with a mean of 319 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ over the 3 year period. The production of the slope region was between 292 and 264 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, with a mean of 280 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ and that of

the open ocean was 220 to 206 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ (mean 217 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹). It is worth emphasising that these annual values are based on daily estimates of primary production.

Figure 8.3. Monthly estimates of depth-integrated primary production for the shelf, slope and open ocean regions in 1998, 1999 and 2000.

8.2.2 Global estimates of primary production: comparison of basin-scale algorithms with other models

This activity was undertaken within the NASA supported Primary Production Algorithm Round Robin 3 (PPARR3) wherein the PROOF PP model was compared with a variety of models operated by laboratories around the world. (It is important to note here that these activities are additional to those specified in the PROOF project “Description of Work” and

the opportunity was grasped to test results funded through PROOF with the leading models from around the world.) Results of the PROOF PP model are shown here in comparison with the other models with permission of the researchers undertaking the global analyses.

The PROOF PP model was run with global input fields as described above. Fig. 8.4 shows the global productivity map for May 1998 using the approach. The map reproduces correctly features such as the Atlantic oligotrophic gyres and the NE Atlantic spring bloom. However the values in the northern polar-regions are probably too high, as are the values off the Benguela upwelling region. The PROOF results were supplied to NASA and a number of comparisons were given in return (used here by kind permission of Mary-Elena Carr, NASA). Fig. 8.5 shows the comparison by ocean basin between the PROOF PP model (number 4) and the other models included in the intercomparison. The PROOF PP model was one of five spectral models; additional models include the Behrenfeld and Falkowski VGPM and a number of Depth Integrated (DINT) approaches.

Figure 8.4. Global productivity map for May 1998 using the PROOF approach. Units are in $mg\ C\ m^{-2}\ d^{-1}$.

It should first be stressed that the PP models are being compared with each other, not with *in situ* data, so the results are with respect to the average of all models. This means that the apparent performance of an individual model depends upon the other models in the

test. Of particular relevance to European scientists, in Fig. 8.5, are the Atlantic and Mediterranean and in both regions the PROOF PP model estimates higher production than the mean: in the Atlantic the estimate is consistently ~10-20% and in the Mediterranean ~10% higher with the exception of the Summer months when production is up to 30% higher.

Figure 8.5. Comparison by month (y-axis) and model (x-axis) for each of the global ocean basins during 1998. The PROOF PP model is a “spectral” model (number 4) and is marked by the vertical box. The scale is shown as the percentage of the mean of all the models.

Figure 8.6. Mean global production in 1998. The PROOF PP model is outlined. The mean of all the models is 49 Gt C year⁻¹.

Figure 8.6 shows the total global estimates of primary production computed through a variety of models. The PROOF PP model, consistent with most spectral models, appears to estimate higher global production than the mean (61 Gt C year⁻¹ of the mean of 49 Gt C year⁻¹).

Finally, Figure 8.7 shows model performance as a function of sea surface temperature. SST is used in the PROOF PP model to vary the *KPUR* parameter (with high SST leading to higher production). For European waters the range of SST would be typically between 5°C and 25°C and it can be seen that for SST between 0°C and 10°C and between 10°C and 20°C the PROOF PP model produces results slightly (~10%) above the average. However, for warmer waters where SST > 20°C the model produces results significantly (20 – 35%) above the mean: this would have particular implications for use of the model in the Mediterranean and in the subtropical and tropical North Atlantic (assuming that the model mean reflects a true value).

Figure 8.7. Model performance as a function of SST. The PROOF PP model is noted.

8.3 The PROOF datasets

PROOF provides two main datasets, respectively based on remote sensing data and on 3-D ecosystem model simulations.

8.3.1 Remote-sensing dataset

Primary production (in mg C m⁻² day⁻¹) maps at 18-km resolution have been produced at different spatial and temporal scales:

- monthly, seasonally and annually averaged maps covering the years from 1997 to 2002 for the entire globe, North Atlantic, Europe, Celtic Sea and English Channel.
- a climatology product corresponding to the average over the six years covered by the project.

Based on the operational methods developed in PROOF, several satellite-derived parameters can be used as an input to the EwE:

- primary production
- seasonal and annual variability of the above parameters (e.g. for an annual simulation in the Ecosim module)
- spatial distribution of these parameters (e.g. accounting for ecosystem habitats in the Ecospace module)

8.3.2 Model outputs

PROOF uses a state-of-the-art 3-D coupled physical-biogeochemical model in order to simulate a number of parameters, which can be used either within the primary production algorithm or as direct products for EwE's users.

The basic quantities derived from the model that can be used in connection with the estimation of primary production from remotely sensed chlorophyll *a* are:

- the vertical (depth) distribution of phytoplankton biomass,
- the vertical (depth) profile of water temperature,
- the mixed layer depth, which can be used to estimate the water layer where primary production is concentrated.

These data have been produced for PROOF as weekly values, and as a seasonal or an annual average.

The basic quantities derived from the model that can sustain the estimation of required parameters in the EwE are:

- the phytoplankton biomass (expressed as $\text{mmol N}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$),
- the 3-D spatial distribution of phytoplankton, zooplankton and detritus to be used within Ecospace,
- the temporal variability of the above parameters to be used within Ecosim.

These latter data has been made available as supporting outputs from PROOF.

8.4 Interface with EwE

An interactive tool has been implemented in order to extract primary production at the different time-scales available, from the remote sensing dataset (Figure 9.2).

This tool allows users to

- browse the PP map database
 - access data produced for the different time-scale (including climatology)
 - access data for the pre-defined regions
 - display time-series of maps
- extract PP values at specific locations and create tables of PP values
- compute statistics on PP estimates

Through simple manipulations, users can extract parameters needed to initialise or validate the EwE models, and can elaborate more advanced information such as seasonal variability patterns, total annual primary production and spatial distribution patterns.

8.4.1 Computing annual primary production

Monthly, seasonal and annual estimates of primary production have calculated from daily SeaWiFS images and then averaged over different periods of time. They are provided in units of $\text{mgC m}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$.

However most EwE ecosystem/regional models are mass-balanced over a period of one year. Therefore primary production is to be provided in units of $\text{tonnes C km}^{-2}\text{yr}^{-1}$.

For regions or ecosystems with limited seasonal variability, one can calculate a usable estimate by applying the following relationship:

$$\text{PP (tonnes C km}^{-2}\text{ yr}^{-1}) = \text{PP (mgC m}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}) * 0.365 \quad (8.1)$$

Otherwise, it is preferred to use monthly estimates as followed:

$$\text{PP (t C/km}^2\text{/yr)} = [(\text{PP}_{\text{Jan}} * 31) + (\text{PP}_{\text{Feb}} * 28) + \dots + (\text{PP}_{\text{Dec}} * 31)] * 10^{-3} \quad (8.2)$$

8.4.2 Deriving seasonal variability pattern

Seasonal variability patterns for a specific year or climatologies, can be produced by browsing each month for the same location. This is made easy since the definition of the location is kept as default when displaying data for specific months.

Twelve values can thus be extracted. Any plotting software can then be used to produce the variability pattern needed for the seasonal forcing of the primary producer in Ecosim.

In Figure 8.8., we present an example of realistic seasonal forcing functions obtained from a time series of SeaWiFS images covering the spring bloom period in 1998 and 1999 for the Celtic Sea.

Figure 8.8. Seasonal variability pattern derived from primary production monthly-averaged maps.

9 DISSEMINATION AND TARGETING USERS

9.1 Worldwide and regional data browsers

In order to enable the results of PROOF to be disseminated as widely and efficiently as possible the data have been interfaced to the internet through a world-wide web site (<http://www.ner-sc.no/PROOF>). Access to the data is currently restricted since the primary production maps were derived from SeaWiFS data, which cannot be used for commercial work in line with NASA’s research agreement with the satellite owner, Orbital Sciences Inc.

Figure 9.1. PROOF website “gallery” showing monthly Primary Production maps for 2000 Europe area

Figure 9.1 above shows the web site in “gallery” mode i.e. with all data for a given year; images can also be viewed for just single months. Clicking on “Extract” under each image leads to the data extraction interface shown in Figure 9.2.

Figure 9.2. Tool to extraction primary production values from the PROOF maps.

This has a number of options: data can be extracted by specifying a latitude/longitude point, or alternatively by moving a cursor over the production image. In addition to the main overview there is a zoom window with X1, X2, X4 and X4 magnification. It is also possible

to construct a list of extraction positions that allow extraction from each image viewed, and hence the construction of a time series. Finally, the mean production for all valid pixels in a 3x3 box centred on the pixel of interest is calculated along with a standard deviation.

9.2 Model output browser for the North Atlantic

A web-based user interface has been implemented in order to ease access to the specific portions of the modelled dataset, as well as to ease extracting EwE-type parameters (mixed layer depth, and vertical profiles of temperature and phytoplankton concentration) data input. The values can be extracted as weekly, monthly or seasonal values from the 1997 model simulations. The parameter values are extracted in tabular form for use in the EwE for a selected location (either through input of lat/long or for a pointing on the map locations) and plotted as vertical profiles for the phytoplankton and temperature. Time series (weekly, monthly or seasonal) of the surface phytoplankton values can also be extracted and plotted for given locations. Figure 9.3 shows the graphical interface for extraction of the modelled parameters developed in PROOF for use in the EwE simulations.

9.3 Towards fisheries management

The practical applications of the satellite Earth observation data sets and numerical ocean and ecosystem model simulations resulting from the PROOF project have wide applications in the science and marine fisheries management community. Proper dissemination of the PROOF results is accordingly of importance for the full exploitation of the project results. In this respect also fisheries management, beyond the science community can find applicability of the PROOF results. The PROOF database, available at <http://www.nersc.no/PROOF>, allows for extraction of the relevant physical and biological parameters for calculation of the annual marine primary production and its seasonal variability to be used as input in marine food chain modelling and consequently fish stock assessment for use in fisheries management.

Figure 9.3 Browsing the PROOF model simulated dataset of the mixed layer depth, vertical temperature distribution and phytoplankton concentration in “Seasonal mode” for 1997. The bathymetry is shown on the graphical map of the Atlantic Ocean, which also can be used for data extraction.

10 CONCLUSIONS AND PLANS FOR THE FUTURE

The PROOF database, available at <http://www.nersc.no/PROOF>, allows extraction of the relevant physical and biological parameters for the calculation of the annual marine primary production and its seasonal variability; this can then be used as an input for marine food chain modelling (such as the Ecopath with Ecosim tool) as a basis for use in fisheries management.

In order to improve the PROOF project dissemination activities the PROOF team suggests that financial resources are made available for a user workshop to present and disseminate the PROOF results and tools to a wider science and fisheries management community including EC DG's. In addition the scientific results of the PROOF project will be presented at a scientific conference, such as ICES 2004, and further scientifically published.

The current PROOF PP model is relatively expensive to run taking 7 hours of CPU time on a Linux Beowulf cluster per global map of productivity. Hence, in an extension of this work the model will use a look-up table (LUT) approach as adopted by Antoine and Morel (1996) with a range of irradiance, chlorophyll, SST and other parameters used to derive it. Additionally, the model could be parallelized to take advantage of the multiple CPU's on the PML cluster.

The Morel model used in PROOF was originally developed for use within case I waters (i.e., where phytoplankton and their associated detrital matter are the only optical components besides the pure water) and has been shown in this report to give good retrievals of productivity in these regions. However, in case II waters where other optically significant components are present, such as Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter and Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM), the model does not give good retrievals of production based on the input fields of chlorophyll, irradiance and SST. It should be stressed that this is not due to incorrect retrieval of chlorophyll from remote sensing data (where appropriate algorithms have been used e.g. section 5.1.2); instead it is the propagation of light within the water column and specifically absorption and scattering by CDOM and SPM that give a factor of up to three difference when compared with *in situ* measurements. The current version of the model uses lookup tables of the spectral diffuse attenuation coefficient for

water and chlorophyll to propagate the spectral light field through the water column. The model could be modified by replacing this diffuse attenuation function with one to read output from the HYDROLIGHT radiative transfer code. HYDROLIGHT could be run using a real or calculated (e.g. Gregg and Carder, 1990) atmosphere with additional functions written to read in spectral measurements of CDOM and SPM, together with the depth variation in chlorophyll. The output of this function would be the surface normalised spectral scalar irradiance, which could then be directly inserted into the model to derive estimates of production.

A parameterisation within the model that needs improvement is the use of a LUT to decompose the broadband PAR field into its spectral components. Currently a run of the Gregg and Carder (1990) model at 50°N for the serial day 181 is used. The integrated irradiance (or PAR) for the Gregg and Carder model is compared with the individual pixel value of PAR and the spectral irradiance scaled up or down accordingly. The spectral irradiance, however, is a function of cloud cover, cloud type (which would be impossible to parameterise) and solar zenith angle. The latter dependency could be better parameterised within the model by having a lookup table of spectral irradiance profiles as a function of the solar zenith angle and using the appropriate profile on a latitudinal basis. The dependency upon cloud amount can be investigated by running the Gregg and Carder model and varying the cloud amount between 0 (clear) and 1 (completely overcast) in 0.1 steps at noon for different latitudes. If there is a linear relationship with the cloud amount then the simplistic parameterisation of linearly scaling the Gregg and Carder LUT spectral irradiance by the LUT integrated PAR to PAR image ratio is correct. In other words this simple scaling implicitly assumes variability in the cloud cover.

The work within PPARR3 will be extended to cover sensitivity analyses for small perturbations of the input parameters of chlorophyll, SST and PAR. This will enable sources of bias and relative error within the model to be identified. The model will also be run in an *in situ* mode using established databases of productivity as inputs. Improvements made by tuning the model to these datasets will feed back into improving the global formulation of the model.

Currently the model uses as input chlorophyll extracted from SeaWiFS data. The model will be extended to use MODIS and MERIS imagery. These sensors have additional products such as spectral absorbance and backscatter, which could be used to improve

propagation of light through the water column. The fine spatial resolution of MERIS (300 m) could be used to produce fine scale maps of production of particular use for narrow coastal bays or estuaries. Higher resolution will also be of use in areas where there is high spatial variability of the optical properties such as within dynamic coastal waters (e.g. the English Channel) or where there are large-scale upwelling events (e.g. off the Iberian Peninsula).

To extend the model to a fully operational status will require efficiencies of coding and the greater use of LUTs. Daily imagery on a pass by pass basis will also be desired for supporting oceanographic cruises and therefore the PML model will have to produce maps of productivity at least an order of magnitude quicker that it currently does (~40 minutes compared with 400 minutes). Parameterisations will be needed to determine daily integrated PAR on a pixel by pixel basis.

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12 GLOSSARY OF SYMBOLS AND ACRONYMS.

Symbol	Units	Definition
ΣPP	$\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$	Integrated primary production (production is integrated at 1 minute intervals over time and to 0.1 % irradiance depth)
$\Sigma PP_{(PUR_{aph})}$	$\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$	Spectral dependent method of computing integrated primary production using total phytoplankton absorption coefficient
$\Sigma PP_{(PAR)}$	$\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$	Spectral independent method of computing integrated primary production
$\Sigma PP_{(BF97)}$	$\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$	Behrenfeld and Falkowski (1997) depth independent primary production satellite algorithm
$\Sigma PP_{(M91)}$	$\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$	Morel (1991) wavelength dependent primary production model
$\Sigma PP_{(NPP)}$	$\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$	Morel (1991) wavelength dependent model of primary production using ϕ_m derived from non photosynthetic pigments using Babin <i>et al.</i> (1996)
P_{opt}^B	$(\text{mg C (mg Chl)}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1})$	Maximum rate of chlorophyll-specific carbon fixation in the water column
E_0	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Sea surface photosynthetically available radiation
Z_{eu}	m	Euphotic irradiance depth
K	m^{-1}	Attenuation coefficient of light
$\phi_{\mu, max}$	$\text{mol C (mol photons)}^{-1}$	Maximum quantum yield of carbon fixation
a_{max}^*	m^{-1}	Maximum chlorophyll specific absorption coefficient
a_{ph}	m^{-1}	Phytoplankton (total pigment) absorption coefficients
a_{ps}	m^{-1}	Phytoplankton photosynthetic pigment absorption coefficients
PAR		Photosynthetically Available Radiation
PUR		Photosynthetically Useable Radiation
PSC	mg m^{-3}	Photosynthetic carotenoids
PPC	mg m^{-3}	Photo protective carotenoids
P_m^B	$\text{mg C (mg Chl)}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$	Light-saturated Chl specific rate of photosynthesis
α^B	$\text{mg C (mg Chl)}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} (\mu\text{E})$	Light limited slope of photosynthesis

	$\text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1})^{-1}$	
E_{PAR}	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	Photosynthetic available radiation
E_{PUR}	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$	Photosynthetic active radiation absorbed by phytoplankton
K_{PUR}	$\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	Irradiance scaling factor
C_{insitu}	mg m^{-3}	<i>In situ</i> chlorophyll a
C_{sat}	mg m^{-3}	Satellite derived chlorophyll a
C	mg m^{-3}	chlorophyll a at the surface (<i>in situ</i> or satellite derived)
Rms		root mean square error
BENG		Benguela Current Coastal Province
ETRA		Eastern Tropical Atlantic Province
CNRY		Eastern (Canary) Coastal Province
NAST-E		North Atlantic Subtropical Gyre Province
NADR		North Atlantic Drift Province